

THE
CORINNIDAE
OF
SOUTH AFRICA

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ABSTRACT

The Corinnidae is a moderately large cosmopolitan family known from 76 genera and 848 species (World Spider Catalog, 2023). The number of genera and species known from South Africa has increased considerably during recent years. Presently, 15 genera represented by 44 species are known from the South Africa, of which 23 species (52%) are South African endemics. Twenty-eight of the species (63%) have a wide range and are of Least Concern, whereas 11 species are Data Deficient. Only five species of the genus *Hortipes* has been identified as species of special concern due to their restricted distributions. A key to the South African genera of Corinnidae is provided.

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FAMILY CORINNIDAE

The Corinnidae is a moderately large cosmopolitan family known from 76 genera and 848 species distributed on all of the continents (World Spider Catalog, 2023). It is currently divided into two subfamilies, Corinninae and Castianeirinae, with the previously included Trachelinae and Phrurolithinae elevated to family level by Ramírez (2014). The number of genera and species known from South Africa has increased considerably during the last two decades, with 15 genera and 44 species presently known from South Africa. Approximately half of the species (23 spp.) are endemics.

COMMON NAMES: Dark sac spiders, ant-like sac spiders.

MORPHOLOGY: Body size: 2–10 mm; male slightly smaller. Colour: most species are cream, yellow-orange, brown or black, often with contrasting dark or light markings, sometimes metallic or ant-like in appearance. Carapace ovoid in dorsal view, sometimes elongate in ant mimics, which are also heavily sclerotized; eyes: eight in two rows (4:4), widely spaced or closely grouped. Abdomen: usually oval, sometimes elongate and rarely with weak constriction in ant-like species; dorsal scutum often present, in males at least; abdomen sometimes with transverse bands, dark mottling or chevron markings; bodies and legs usually with recumbent, feathery setae that often form lines or patterns. Legs: sturdy, but usually long and thin in ant mimics; leg spines present.

LIFESTYLE: Most corinnids are free-running, nocturnal spiders that actively hunt prey on the ground. Some species rest during the day in a silk retreat, while others hide under rocks, in leaf litter or in grass tussocks. Some of the ant-mimics are diurnal. Some genera, e.g. *Merenius*, *Castianeira* and *Apochinomma* mimic ants (Formicidae), while *Graptartia* and *Coenoptychus* are mimics of wingless female velvet ants (Mutillidae). Four genera, *Copa*, *Copuetta*, *Echinax* and *Messapus*, are cryptically coloured and closely resemble wolf spiders (Lycosidae) in general appearance. Most of the genera are found in open grassland and savanna habitats, but *Cambalida*, *Copa*, *Hortipes* and *Pronophaea* are strongly associated with leaf litter in woodland and forest habitats. Many of the ground-dwelling species are associated with leaf litter, but certain genera (e.g. *Vendaphaea*) are more often collected at the bases of grass tussocks. One species, *Copuetta lacustris*, is synanthropic and often found around human habitation. The eggs sacs of corinnids are dome-shaped, have a shiny, papery appearance and texture, and are usually constructed under stones, logs or leaves on the soil surface, or under bark or leaves in trees.

TAXONOMY: Many of the genera have been revised or had species redescribed: *Hortipes* (Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000); *Graptartia* and *Coenoptychus* (Haddad, 2004; Paul *et al.*, 2018); *Corinnomma* (Haddad, 2006); *Austrophaea* (Haddad, 2007); *Vendaphaea* (Haddad, 2009); *Cambalida* (Haddad, 2012a); *Echinax* (Haddad, 2012b); *Apochinomma* (Haddad, 2013a); *Copa* (Haddad, 2013b); *Copuetta* (Haddad, 2013c); *Medmassa* (Haddad & Bosselaers, 2010); *Merenius* (Haddad & Louw, 2012); *Messapus* (Haddad, 2013c; Haddad & Mbo, 2015); *Pronophaea* (Haddad & Bosselaers, 2010).

Figures 1–4. Representative species of Corinnidae from South Africa: 1. *Apochinomma formicae-forme*. 2. *Austrophaea zebra*. 3. *Castianeira* sp. (undescribed). 4. *Copa flavoplumosa*. Photo credits: Charles Haddad.

FAMILY CORINNIDAE

KEY TO THE GENERA OF SOUTH AFRICAN CORINNIDAE

1. Tiny yellow spiders, usually <3 mm in length, with modified oval grouping of erect setae on anterior metatarsi.....*Hortipes*
 - Generally larger spiders, >3 mm in length, with variable body colouration, without an oval group of modified setae on anterior metatarsi.....2
2. Tibia I with at least four pairs of ventral spines; palpal tegulum oval, with conductor and median apophysis present; female epigyne usually with large paired oval atria or single subtriangular median atrium, extending to epigastric furrow, rarely with oblique diamond-shaped median septum with lateral copulatory openings (*Pronophaea* group).....3
 - Tibia I usually with at most three pairs of ventral spines, rarely with six or more pairs (*Medmassa*); male palpal tegulum oval or pear-shaped, without median apophysis or conductor, rarely with tegular apophysis present; female epigyne with paired copulatory openings surrounded by sclerotized ridges or depressions, not extending to epigastric furrow.....5
3. PME closer to each other than to PLE; body and legs densely covered in short fine setae, giving them a velvety appearance; retrolateral tibial apophysis originating basally on tibia, curved, with denticles at tip; epigyne with diamond-shaped median septum.....*Vendaphaea*
 - PME as far from each other as from PLE; body and legs sparsely covered in short fine setae; retrolateral tibial apophysis originating distally; epigyne with large paired oval atria separated by tongue-like septum or single median subtriangular atrium.....4
4. Body pale yellow, with dark median stripe on carapace and abdomen, transverse chevron markings on abdomen, and black tibia and metatarsus I; tibiae and metatarsi I and II slightly dorso-ventrally flattened.....*Austrophaea*
 - Body generally uniform in colour, sometimes with chevron markings on abdomen, but legs I uniform in colour; tibiae and metatarsi I and II cylindrical.....*Pronophaea*
5. Palpal tegulum oval, with prolateral-distal tegular apophysis and retrolaterally-curved embolus (*Corinninae*).....*Messapus*
 - Palpal tegulum teardrop- or pear-shaped, with only a distal coiled or short curved embolus present (*Castianeirinae*).....6
6. Posterior eye row procurved.....7
 - Posterior eye row straight or recurved.....13
7. Tibia I with at least six pairs of ventral spines; palpal tegulum teardrop-shaped with curved embolus, and palpal tibia with large retrolateral apophysis; female epigyne with single large oval spermathecae with anteromedian copulatory openings.....*Medmassa*
 - Tibia I with no more than three pairs of ventral spines; palpal tegulum pear-shaped, clearly narrowed distally, with coiled embolus; palpal tibia usually without apophysis; if present, very short; female epigyne usually with distinctly separate anterior and posterior spermathecae, copulatory openings usually laterally in epigyne.....8
8. Carapace colouration similar to that of Lycosidae, i.e. cream, grey or orange-brown with paired black markings laterally of midline.....9
 - Carapace usually uniform in colouration, i.e. orange, red, brown or black, occasionally with markings comprising white plumose setae or black striae.....11
9. All patellae with proximal seta and long distal spine, longer than patella; diameter of AME nearly double that of ALE.....*Echinax*
 - Anterior patellae only with long fine proximal and distal setae, posterior patellae with long fine seta and distal seta or spine, always shorter than patella; diameter of AME less than 1.5 times that of ALE.....10
10. PER strongly procurved, transverse line from anterior margin of PME passing through posterior half of PLE; carapace width more than 3.3 times PER width.....*Copa*
 - PER slightly procurved, transverse line from anterior margin of PME passing through anterior half of PLE; carapace width usually less than 3 times PER width.....*Copuetta*
11. Carapace texture coarsely granulate; cephalic region clearly narrowed anteriorly, PER very strongly procurved; abdominal surface covered in clavate and straight setae.....*Graptartia*
 - Carapace texture finely granulate or wrinkled; cephalic region only slightly narrowed anteriorly, PER slightly procurved; abdominal surface covered in plumose and short straight setae.....12
12. AER with ALE clearly larger than AME; carapace width less than 2.5 times PER width; male palpal cymbium with 6–10 large thickened black setae arranged in two or three rows, close to distal end of dorsal surface; female epigastric scutum weakly sclerotised, epigyne usually with somewhat indistinct weakly sclerotised ridges.....*Cambalida*
 - AER with AME usually slightly larger than ALE, rarely smaller; carapace width usually more than 2.6 times PER width; male palpal cymbium without long thickened distal setae, sometimes with two or three short thickened or bent setae distally; female epigastric scutum usually strongly sclerotised, epigyne with distinct hardened ridges.....*Castianeira*
13. Eyes very small, PER very strongly recurved; posterior eyes separated by more than 1½ times their diameter, PME usually closer to each other than to PLE; carapace very elongate and narrow, length more than 1.6 times width, usually more than 1.8 times width; mimics of ants with abdomen globose or elongate with shallow constriction.....*Apochinomma*
 - Eyes larger, PER slightly recurved or nearly straight; posterior eyes separated by distance less than 1¼ times their diameter, PME closer to PLE than to each other; carapace elongate oval, length less than 1.6 times width; mimics of ants or velvet ants, but abdomen oval.....14
14. Thoracic region of carapace covered in plumose and long erect straight setae; abdomen black, with white or cream median triangular or star-shaped marking and three white spots around spinnerets.....*Coenoptychus*
 - Thoracic region of carapace with plumose and scattered adpressed short straight setae; abdomen with black transverse bands or serrated white marking along dorsal midline.....15
15. Abdomen with black transverse bands; femora II with three dorsal spines only; tibiae II with at least one pair of ventral spines.....*Corinnomma*
 - Abdomen with symmetrical white marking along dorsal midline; femora II with one prolateral spine and three dorsal spines; tibiae II with only a single retrolateral ventral spine.....*Merenius*

GENUS *APOCHINOMMA* Pavesi, 1881

The genus *Apochinomma* Pavesi, 1881 is represented by 16 species is recorded from the Afrotropical, Neotropical, and Oriental Regions (World Spider Catalog, 2023), but it remains unclear whether the genus is monophyletic. They belong to the Castianeirinae and are generally regarded as good examples of Batesian mimics of ants (Hymenoptera: Formicidae): African members of the *formicaeforme* group are mimics of *Polyrhachis* ants that occur on foliage and the soil surface, while species in the *decepta* species group are mimics of large, ground-dwelling ponerine ants.

COMMON NAMES: *Apochinomma* ant-like sac spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Apochinomma formicaeforme* Pavesi, 1881

MORPHOLOGY: *Apochinomma* species can be recognised by the elongate cephalothorax, which is usually more than twice as long as it is wide, sometimes with a shallow median constriction. Their small and widely-spaced posterior eyes are in a recurved row, with the eyes usually widely separated by more than twice their diameter. They have an orange-brown to black carapace, with black mottling and striae, and the surface is finely to coarsely granulate, covered in short straight and plumose setae, with several long curved setae on the clypeus and eye region. Their leg formula is 4-1-2-3. The abdomen is pear-shaped, or elongate with a median constriction, with an elongate petiole anteriorly. The body setae are generally a silvery-grey in colour, with black setae forming distinct markings on the legs, carapace and abdomen.

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground- and foliage-dwellers. The Afrotropical members of the genus display various morphological adaptations to ant mimicry. Several species have a median depression on the cephalothorax, an elongate pedicel, and a variable abdominal shape that resembles the abdomen of ants.

TAXONOMY: The Afrotropical species were revised by Haddad (2013a) and six species were recognized, of which two were recorded from South Africa, with an additional third undescribed species from the Western Cape that was only known from juveniles. A third described species (*A. elongatum*) was subsequently recorded from the country (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022).

Figure 1–2. 1. *Apochinomma elongata*, habitus. 2. Same, eye pattern. Photo credits: Peter Webb.

Apochinomma decepta Haddad, 2013

COMMON NAME: Maputaland *Apochinomma* ant-like sac spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern Africa endemic described by Haddad (2013) from Tembe Elephant Park in KwaZulu-Natal. Known also from Mozambique. In South Africa, it has been recorded from two provinces, including three protected areas (EOO = 1649 km²; AOO = 12 km²; 47–256 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mozambique and South Africa.

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground-dweller. This spider was collected from coastal woodlands, wetlands and swamps, usually at altitudes lower than 50 m a.s.l., with a well-developed grass layer. This species is most likely a mimic of medium to large ponerine ants, such as *Streblognatha* and *Pachycondyla*, but further study is needed to assess whether a single species serves as its model.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve, Shokwe Pan (-26.87, 32.21); Tembe Elephant Park, Muzi Swamps (-27.00, 32.49). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park, Skukuza (-24.95, 31.67).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is known from two countries and conserved in three protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes. Carapace elongate oval, eye region broad, tapering posteriorly to pedicel, broadest at coxa II; raised from eye region, highest at one-third carapace length, nearly level in midsection, declining gradually in posterior third; surface finely granulate, covered in short straight white setae and sparse white feathery setae; several long erect setae on clypeus, in and behind eye region; fovea short, narrow, positioned between one-half and two-thirds carapace length; carapace dark red-brown with extensive black mottling and distinct striae. All eyes with black rings. Abdomen elongate, pear-shaped, with distinct transverse constriction near middle; dorsally with narrow anterior black band, n-shaped marking in anterior half, and broad bank posterior to constriction. Legs slender, with narrow lengthwise stripes (Haddad, 2013a).

Figures 1–6. *Apochinomma decepta*. 1. Female habitus. 2–4. Male habitus. 5. Male palp, ventral view. 6. Epigyne, ventral view. Photo credits: 1–4 Charles Haddad. 5–6 From Haddad (2013a).

Apochinomma elongatum Haddad, 2013

COMMON NAME: Long *Apochinomma* ant-like sac spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic species that was described by Haddad (2013a) from Botswana. It has been collected from four African countries. This species is possibly under-collected and suspected to occur in more African countries. From South Africa it has only been collected from Gauteng and KwaZulu-Natal. Due to its wide geographical range in Africa, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Malawi, Tanzania and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Irene, Centurion, field opposite Gem Village (-25.89, 28.23). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve, Nyamiti Pan (-26.89, 32.31).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground-dweller. In South Africa, sampled from the Grassland and Savanna Biomes (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022). The paratype specimen recorded from Malawi is the largest African ant-mimicking corinnid, measuring 13.6 mm in total length.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is known from four African countries and protected in the Ndumo Game Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: The records of *A. elongatum* from Irene and Ndumo Game Reserve represent the first for South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022). Known from only the male. Carapace elongate oval, eye region broad, tapering posteriorly to pedicel, broadest at coxa II; raised from eye region, highest at one-third carapace length, nearly level in midsection, with very slight median depression, declining gradually in posterior one-third; surface finely granulate, covered in short straight white setae, with sparse white feathery setae; several long erect setae on clypeus and in eye region; fovea short, narrow, at two-thirds carapace length; carapace deep red-brown with faint black striae, black mottling on clypeus, in and behind eye region and along lateral margins of carapace. All eyes with faded black rings (Haddad, 2013a).

Figures 1–5. *Apochinomma elongatum*, male: 1–2. Habitus. 3. Eyes, anterior view. 4. Palp, embolus. 5. Male palp, ventral view. 6. Same, retrolateral-ventral view. 7. Same, retrolateral view. Photo credits: 1–3 Peter Webb. 4–7 From Haddad (2013a).

Apochinomma formicaeforme Pavesi, 1881

COMMON NAME: African *Apochinomma* ant-like sac spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1881 from Mozambique. The species is known from several countries throughout the Afrotropical Region. In South Africa, it is known from four provinces (EOO = 239 925 km²; AOO = 100 km²; 8–1171 m a.s.l.). Due to its geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Widespread throughout Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **KwaZulu-Natal:** Dukuduku Forest Station (-28.37, 32.23); Durban, Bluff (-29.88, 31.02); Empangeni (-28.75, 31.90); Enseleni Nature Reserve (-28.68, 32.05); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Hell's Gate (-28.00, 32.48); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.40, 32.76); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, St Lucia (28.08, 32.42); Smith's Farm (-28.33, 32.42); La Mercy (-29.63, 31.13); Ingwavuma, Mac's Pass (-27.13, 32.00); KwaNgwanase, Coastal Cashews (-27.11, 32.57); KwaNgwanase, Manguzi Forest (-26.97, 32.73); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.88, 32.25); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.37, 31.39); Phinda Game Reserve (-27.72, 32.38); 15 km N of Richards Bay (-28.83, 32.08); Tembe Elephant Park (-27.07, 32.45). **Limpopo:** Tzaneen (-23.82, 30.16); Vhembe Biosphere, Mashovelo Lodge (-22.94, 29.89); Tshulu Camp (-22.58, 30.81). **Mpumalanga:** Burger's Hall (-25.10, 31.07); Embuleni Nature Reserve (-25.95, 30.55); Kruger National Park, Shabenikop (-25.08, 31.27). **North West:** Kwasgani Nature Reserve (-25.65, 27.22).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living wanderer, collected from the foliage of trees and shrubs in the Forest, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species and it is widespread throughout Africa. It is conserved in several protected areas, including Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2006), Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad *et al.*, 2010) and Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2015).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Redescribed by Haddad (2013a). Carapace elongate oval. Abdomen covered in white plumose setae, with broad black bands; in male, dorsal scutum is black, covering entire dorsum, but it is small in females; abdomen pear-shaped, broad and round posteriorly, with long pedicel. Legs dark. Known from both sexes.

Figures 1–9. *Apochinomma formicaeforme*. 1–3. Female habitus. 4. Male habitus. 5–6. Male palp, ventral view. 7. Same, retrolateral view. 8. Female epigyne, ventral view. 9. Same, dorsal view. Photo credits: 1–2 Rudolph Steenkamp. 3 Ondrej Michalek. 4, 5 Charles Haddad. 6–9 From Haddad (2013a).

GENUS *AUSTROPHAEA* Lawrence, 1952

The genus *Austrophaea* Lawrence, 1952 is monotypic and endemic to South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2023).

COMMON NAME: *Austrophaea* dark sac spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Austrophaea zebra* Lawrence, 1952

MORPHOLOGY: *Austrophaea* specimens can be easily recognised by the very robust anterior legs, particularly the tibiae and metatarsi, which are enlarged and broad, and very strongly spined ventrally; the carapace is somewhat flattened, with a median black longitudinal stripe, and the abdomen bears a black median stripe and 5–7 posterior transverse chevron markings. Medium-sized spiders, 4.5–6.5 mm in length; cream to deep yellow-orange in colour, with black markings on carapace and abdomen. Carapace slightly convex, somewhat flattened, slightly narrowed behind eye region and invaginated posteriorly; widest at second coxae. Abdomen oval, tapering posteriorly; male with narrow dorsal scutum, absent in females; ventral sclerites absent. Legs I longest, with greatly enlarged tibiae and metatarsi; remaining legs with narrow black rings on femora, patellae, tibiae and metatarsi; femora of legs I strongly spined on prolateral margin, tibiae and metatarsi of legs I and II strongly spined ventrally; leg formula 1423.

LIFESTYLE: *Austrophaea* is only known from low-lying grasslands, savannah, and coastal forests in the eastern parts of South Africa, and is probably an exclusively ground-dwelling spider, as no specimens have been collected from foliage. The specimens collected at Kei Mouth were found in leaf litter between grasses in the ecotone between coastal forests and adjacent grassland.

TAXONOMY: The genus was revised by Haddad (2007).

Figures 1–2. *Austrophaea zebra*. 1. Male habitus. 2. Eye pattern. Photo credits: 1 Charles Haddad. 2 Rudi Steenkamp.

Austrophaea zebra Lawrence, 1952

COMMON NAME: Zebra Dark Sac Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 1952 from Tongaat in KwaZulu-Natal. The species is known from two provinces (EOO = 34 289 km²; AOO = 44 km²; 47 –696 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographic range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Alexandria (-33.65, 26.40); Kei Mouth (-32.68, 28.37); Mzimhlava River Mouth (-31.38, 29.52); Port Shepstone (-30.72, 30.46); Silaka Nature Reserve (-31.65, 29.50). *KwaZulu-Natal:* Ashburton (-29.67, 30.45); Port Edward, Farm Blencantra (-31.03, 30.17); Pietermaritzburg (-29.60, 30.38); Port Edward (-31.05, 30.22); Scottburgh (-30.29, 30.75); Tongaat (-29.56, 31.12).

LIFESTYLE: Known only from low-lying grasslands, savanna and coastal forests in the eastern parts of South Africa. The species is exclusively ground-dwelling, and has been collected from leaf litter between grasses in the ecotone between coastal forests and adjacent grassland. Sampled from the Thicket, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threatened by loss of habitat for crop farming around Scottburgh and Pietermaritzburg, and infrastructure development for Pietermaritzburg, Port Edward and Port Shepstone. However, it has been recorded from several protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Haddad (2007). Carapace slightly convex and somewhat flattened, carapace pale cream-yellow to deep yellow-orange, with broad median dark brown mottled stripe extending from anterior eye row to posterior margin of carapace and dark brown spots laterally at bases of coxae II, III and IV. All eyes with black rings. Abdomen oval-elongate, with narrow brown dorsal scutum extending to two-thirds, and black median stripe dividing into several transverse chevron markings posteriorly. Legs I robust, with yellow femora, patellae and tarsi, and black tibiae and metatarsi; remaining legs shorter, cream, with black bands.

Figures 1–7. *Austrophaea zebra*. 1–3. Male habitus. 4–5. Male palp. 6. Female epigyne. 7. Male legs I and II. Photo credits: 1 Rudi Steenkamp. 2–4 Charles Haddad. 5–7 From Haddad (2007).

GENUS *CAMBALIDA* Simon, 1909

The genus *Cambalida* Simon, 1909 is represented by 15 species (World Spider Catalog, 2023). Two species known from South Africa.

COMMON NAME: *Cambalida* dark sac spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Cambalida insulana* Simon, 1909

MORPHOLOGY: This genus can be recognised by the relatively broader carapace compared to other castianeirines, anterior lateral eyes that are usually considerably larger than the anterior median eyes and the posterior eyes that are larger than those of the anterior eye row. The posterior eyes are less than one diameter apart. Males can further be distinguished by the presence of two or three rows of very distinct, longer thickened setae at the distal end of the dorsal surface of the palpal cymbium. The dorsal abdominal scutum covers the entire abdomen in males but only the anterior parts in females.

LIFESTYLE: *Cambalida* are entirely ground-dwelling and are mainly associated with savanna and forest habitats on the continent, although two species occurring in southern Africa are also found in drier grassland, Nama Karoo and/or fynbos habitats.

TAXONOMY: The genus was revised by Haddad (2012a). Subsequently, several species have been recognized from India and the genus has also been identified from samples in Israel and North Africa.

Figures 1–3. 1. Female *Cambalida* sp. from Pongola 2. *Cambalida dippenaarae*, male habitus. 3. Same, female habitus. Photo credits: 1 Ruan Booysen. 2–3 Charles Haddad.

Cambalida dippenarae Haddad, 2012

COMMON NAME: Dippenaar's *Cambalida* Dark Sac Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 2012 from Zambia. It has been collected from six southern African countries (EOO = 674 364 km²; AOO = 152 km²; 3–1560 m a.s.l.). In South Africa it is known from eight provinces, including >10 protected areas. Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Zambia, Botswana, Mozambique, Zimbabwe, Namibia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park, Woody Cape (-33.57, 25.68); Cwebbe Nature Reserve (-32.28, 28.90); Great Fish River Reserve (-26.65, 33.13); Kei Mouth (-32.68, 28.37); Sterkstroom, Farm Wilgerskloof (-31.60, 26.37); St. Francis Bay (-34.16, 24.83); Sundays River Valley (-33.39, 25.43). **Free State:** Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Bloemfontein, Farm Deelhoek (-28.85, 26.12); Bloemfontein, Farm Hopefield (-28.90, 26.23); Bloemfontein, Free State National Botanical Gardens (-29.11, 26.22); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.50, 26.79); Florisbad Research Station (-28.77, 26.08); Kalkfontein Dam Nature Reserve (-29.51, 25.25); Ladybrand, Farm De Luc (-29.29, 27.40); Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.80, 25.72); Sandveld Nature Reserve (-27.85, 25.93); Tussen-die-Riviere Nature Reserve (-30.49, 26.18); Willem Pretorius Nature Reserve (-28.28, 27.20). **Gauteng:** Alice Glockner Nature Reserve (-26.74, 28.38); Johannesburg, Florida (-26.18, 27.91); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve (-26.31, 28.01); Kloofendal Nature Reserve (-26.14, 27.86); Krugersdorp, Hekpoort Farm (-25.95, 27.63); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Empangeni (-28.75, 31.90); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.10); Hluhluwe-Imfolozi Park, Hilltop Research Station (-28.07, 32.04); Hluhluwe, Umkhuzi Pan (-27.67, 32.30); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Eastern Shores Nature Reserve (-29.09, 32.16); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, False Bay Park (-27.92, 32.27); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Fanie's Island (-28.53, 32.40); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Hell's Gate (-28.00, 32.48); Ithala Game Reserve (-27.51, 31.23); Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); Mfongosi (-27.28, 32.15); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.37, 31.39); Pietermaritzburg (-29.55, 30.35); 15 km N of Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.10); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Umgeni Valley Nature Reserve (-29.47, 30.20). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Klein Kariba, near Bela-Bela (-24.88, 28.29); Lajuma Mountain Retreat (-23.03, 29.45); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16); Little Leigh (-22.95, 29.87); Mabula Lodge, near Bela-Bela (-24.84, 27.96); Makalali Nature

Figures 1–7. *Cambalida dippenarae*. 1, 3. Female habitus. 2. Male habitus. 4. Male palp. 5, 6. Epigyne, ventral view. 7. Same, dorsal view. Photo credits: Charles Haddad.

Cambalida dippenarae (continued)

Reserve (-24.34, 30.93); Mussina (-22.34, 30.03); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Roedtan (-24.60, 29.08); Settlers (-24.95, 28.52); Springbokvlakte, Bekendevelei (-25.01, 28.88); Springbok Flats, Bekendevelei (-24.90, 28.73); Tshulu (-22.58, 30.81).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground-dweller. Fairly common and collected by litter sifting and pitfall traps in forest and savanna habitats, and occasionally from the Grassland, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Nama Karoo biomes. It was also sampled from citrus and grapefruit orchards and cotton and maize fields.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is recorded from several protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Haddad, 2012). Carapace deep red-brown with black mottling, clypeus dark brown medially, yellow-brown laterally, eye region nearly black; faint black striae radiating from fovea towards palps and leg coxae; surface granulate, sparsely covered in white plumose setae; eyes with black rings; legs finely granulate; femora I–IV dark brown; abdomen dark grey, with large dark red brown dorsal scutum. abdomen with fine cream chevrons posteriorly and small white spot of dense plumose setae just above spinnerets.

Figures 8–11. *Cambalida dippenarae*. 8. Male palp, ventral view. 9. Same, retrolateral view. 10. Epigyne, ventral view. 11. Same, dorsal view. From Haddad (2012a).

Figure 12. *Cambalida dippenarae*, female habitus. Photo credit: Peter Webb.

Cambalida fulvipes Simon, 1896

COMMON NAME: Common *Cambalida* dark sac spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic species described in 1896 from Gauteng, South Africa. It has been collected from several countries throughout the Afrotropical Region. In South Africa, it is known from all nine provinces (EOO = 824 703 km²; AOO = 216 km²; 16–1722 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Widely distributed throughout Afrotropical Region.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Bamboeshoek, Farm Bamboesberg (-31.62, 26.35); Fort Beaufort, Mpofu Nature Reserve (-32.78, 26.62); Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43); St. Francis Bay (-34.13, 24.84). **Free State:** Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.61, 26.43); Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Bloemfontein, Bains Vlei (-29.05, 26.08); Bloemfontein, Farm Deelhoek (-28.83, 26.08); Bloemfontein, Farm Hopefield (-28.90, 26.23); Bloemfontein, Free State National Botanical Gardens (-29.05, 26.21); Clocolan, Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.80, 27.65); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.50, 26.80); Florisbad Research Station (-28.77, 26.07); Ladybrand, Farm De Luc (-29.30, 27.40); Sandveld Nature Reserve (-27.85, 25.93); Willem Pretorius Game Reserve (-28.28, 27.20). **Gauteng:** Florida (-26.18, 27.91), Heidelberg, Alice Glockner Nature Reserve (-26.50, 28.36); Krugersdorp/Mogale, Farm Hekpoort (-26.09, 27.78); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Empangeni (-28.72, 31.88); Hlatikulu (-26.95, 31.30); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve, Hilltop Camp (-28.09, 32.10); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Cape Vidal (-28.16, 32.56); Marlevale Bird Sanctuary (-26.25, 28.67); Mfongosi (-27.28, 32.15); Ndumo Game Reserve, Crocodile Farm (-26.54, 32.15); Ndumo Game Reserve, Dipini Hide (-26.86, 32.26); Ndumo Game Reserve, E shore Shokwe Pan (-26.88, 32.21); Ndumo Game Reserve, Red Cliffs (-26.85, 32.21); Ndumo Game Reserve, W shore Nyamiti Pan (-26.91, 32.28); Pietermaritzburg (-29.60, 30.38); Tembe Elephant Park (-27.03, 32.42); Umgeni Valley Nature Reserve (-29.47, 30.20). **Limpopo:** Klein Kariba (-24.88, 28.29); Komatipoort (-25.43, 31.94); Lajuma Mountain Retreat (-23.04, 29.45); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.04, 29.44); Makelali Nature Reserve (-24.34, 30.93); Messina/Mussina (-22.34, 30.03); Settlers (-24.95, 28.52); Springbokvlakte, Bekendevelei (-25.01, 28.88); Tshulu Camp (-22.58, 30.81). **Mpumalanga:** Acornhoek (-24.58, 31.10); Bethal (-26.44, 29.46); Delmas, farm Rietvallei (-26.08, 28.57); Kruger National Park, 6 km S of Skukuza (-24.98, 31.59). **North West:**

Figures 1–4. *Cambalida fulvipes*. 1, 2. Female habitus. 3. Male habitus. 4. Male palp. Photo credits: 1 Rudi Steenkamp. 2–4 Charles Haddad.

Cambalida fulvipes Simon, 1896

Brits (-25.62, 27.77); Vryburg, Farm Weltevrede (-27.41, 24.51). **Northern Cape:** Farm Pniel (-28.58, 24.52); Schmidtsdrift, Farm Geelkoppies (-28.73, 23.88). **Western Cape:** De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.29, 20.29); Fisherhaven, Hermanus district (-34.47, 19.27); Gamkaskloof, Die Hel (-33.36, 21.69); Rondeberg (-33.48, 18.32); Swartberg Nature Reserve, Montagu Baths (-33.79, 20.13).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground-dweller that occupies the greatest range of habitats, including tropical and temperate forests and the Savanna, Grassland, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Nama Karoo and Fynbos biomes (Haddad *et al.*, 2013 and Foord *et al.*, 2011). Also sampled from maize fields and pistachio orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is protected in several protected areas such as De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009), Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2015) and the Amanzi Private Game Reserve (Haddad & Butler, 2018).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Redescribed by Haddad (2012a) and known from both sexes.

Figures 5–10. *Cambalida fulvipes*. 5, 6. Male palp, ventral view. 7. Same, retrolateral view. 8, 9. Epigyne, ventral view. 10. Same, dorsal view. Photo credits: 5, 8 Charles Haddad. 6, 7, 9, 10 From Haddad (2012a).

GENUS *COENOPTYCHUS* Simon, 1885

The genus *Coenoptychus* Simon, 1885 is represented by three species (World Spider Catalog, 2023), with two species known from the Afrotropical Region, both of which occur in South Africa.

COMMON NAME: Dwarf mutilliform sac spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Coenoptychus pulcher* Simon, 1885

MORPHOLOGY: Carapace gradually raised towards rear; highest at approximately two-thirds its length; surface granular; long straight and short feathery setae scattered throughout; fovea broad and indistinct, slightly posterior to midpoint of carapace; carapace deep orange to reddish-brown to dark brown throughout, with brown rings present around eyes; anterior row strongly procurved, posterior row slightly recurved; eyes subequal in size. Abdomen oval, with large dorsal scutum; dorsum with black undertone, covered with short, black feathery setae and long erect straight setae; creamy-white feathery setae making intricate geometrical markings on abdomen. Legs orange-brown with black bands on femora, densely covered in creamy-white feathery setae. Genital plate of females heavily sclerotized. Male smaller and more slender than female.

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground-dwellers that resemble the wingless females of smaller genera of velvet ants (Hymenoptera: Mutillidae).

TAXONOMY: The two Afrotropical species were originally described in *Graptartia* Simon, 1896 by Haddad (2004), and were recently transferred to *Coenoptychus* by Paul *et al.* (2018).

Figures 1–2. *Coenoptychus mutillicus*. 1. Female habitus. 2. Eye pattern. Photo credits: Rudi Steenkamp.

Coenoptychus mutillicus (Haddad, 2004)

COMMON NAME: Elegant dwarf mutilliform sac spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 2004 from the Deelhoek Farm near Bloemfontein in the Free State. The species is known from ten other African countries. In South Africa, the species is known from six of the nine provinces, including several protected areas (EOO = 402 597 km²; AOO = 76 km²; 93–1951 m a.s.l.). There are no significant known threats to the species. Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Lesotho, Botswana, Burkino Faso, Cameroon, Kenya, Ethiopia, Ivory Coast, Nigeria, South Africa, Tanzania and Zimbabwe.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Bloemfontein, Farm Deelhoek (-30.98, 23.81); Bloemfontein, Farm Hopefield (-28.90, 26.23); Bloemfontein, Valley of Seven Dams Conservancy (-26.04, 29.13); Brandfort, Florisbad Research Station (-28.70, 26.45); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.50, 26.80); Smithfield (-30.21, 26.53); Vaal Dam (-26.90, 28.12); Willem Pretorius Nature Reserve (-28.28, 27.20). **Gauteng:** Johannesburg, Wonderboom (-25.65, 28.65). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Howick, Lake Midmar (-29.50, 30.22); Tembe Elephant Park (-27.03, 32.42). **Limpopo:** Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.90, 29.47); Tuinplaas, Springbokvlakte (-24.90, 28.73). **Mpumalanga:** Delmas, Farm Rietvallei (-26.08, 28.57); Steenkampsberg, Grobler's Farm (-25.50, 30.10); Verloren Vallei Nature Reserve (-25.53, 30.13). **Northern Cape:** Kuruman, Farm Mansfield (-27.46, 23.43).

LIFESTYLE: The species is known from a variety of habitats, but appears to prefer the Grassland and Savanna biomes. It is usually collected in pitfall traps and leaf litter, or under prone objects, where it shelters when not active. These objects include stones, dry cattle dung pads, logs, and in abandoned mounds of the snouted harvester termite, *Trinervitermes trinervoides*. From crops it was also sampled from maize fields.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is recorded from several protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Haddad, 2004).

Figures 1–9. *Coenoptychus mutillicus*. 1, 4. Male habitus. 2. Female habitus. 3. Female, lateral view. 5, 7. Male palp, ventral view. 6, 8. Same, retrolateral view. 9. Epigyne, ventral view. Photo credits: 1 Rudi Steenkamp. 2–3 Peter Webb. 4–6 Charles Haddad. 7–9 From Haddad (2004).

Coenoptychus tropicalis (Haddad, 2004)

COMMON NAME: Tropical dwarf mutilliform sac spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 2004 from Tanzania as *Graptartia tropicalis*. The species is also known from four other African countries. In South Africa, it is known from six provinces including ten protected areas (EOO = 722 262 km²; AOO = 96 km²; 2–1587 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats known to the species, and due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Tanzania, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Kenya, Ivory Coast and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Bamboesberg, Farm Bamboeshoek (-31.62, 26.35); Coffee Bay (-31.97, 29.14); Colchester (-33.69, 25.82); Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Kei River Mouth (-32.68, 28.37); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); 60 km N of Port Elizabeth (-33.30, 25.90). **Free State:** Bloemfontein, Farm Hopefield (-28.90, 26.23); Bloemfontein, Free State National Botanical Gardens (-29.05, 26.21); Tussen-die-Riviere Nature Reserve (-30.49, 26.18). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Drummond (-29.75, 30.70); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Hell's Gate (-28.00, 32.48); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Gwala-Gwala Forest (-28.38, 32.41); Ithala Game Reserve (-27.51, 31.23); Mfongosi (-27.82, 32.15) Ndumo Game Reserve, N shore of Nyamiti Pan (-26.87, 32.24); Pietermaritzburg (-29.55 30.35); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Umgeni Valley Nature Reserve (-29.47, 30.20). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park, 3 km W of Letaba (-23.87, 31.53); Soutpansberg, Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.038, 29.442). **North West:** Venterskroon, Thabela Thabang Mountain Retreat (-26.86, 28.30). **Western Cape:** De Hoop Nature Reserve, Koppie Alleen (-34.49, 20.43); Fisherhaven, Hermanus District (-34.42, 19.143); Swartberg Nature Reserve, Gamkaskloof (-33.36, 21.69).

LIFESTYLE: This species has been recorded from all the biomes except Succulent and Nama Karoo. They inhabit grasslands and leaf litter and has been collected from Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Grassland, Fynbos, Savannah and Forest biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is recorded from several protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Haddad, 2004).

Figures 1–9. *Coenoptychus tropicalis*. 1, 2. Female habitus. 3. Immature habitus. 4. Male habitus. 5, 6. Male palp, ventral view. 7. Same, retrolateral view. 8. Epigyne, ventral view. Photo credits: 1 Ondrej Michalek. 2, 4, 5 Charles Haddad. 3 Peter Webb. 6–8 From Haddad (2004).

GENUS *COPA* Simon, 1885

The genus *Copa* is represented by seven species, of which two are known from South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2023). One is widespread throughout the Afrotropical Region (*C. flavoplumosa* Simon, 1885) and the other is endemic to south-eastern South Africa (*C. kei* Haddad, 2013).

COMMON NAME: Ground lycosiform sac spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Copa flavoplumosa* Simon, 1885

MORPHOLOGY: They are medium-sized spiders and their carapace is usually pale yellow to dark orange-brown with black markings, rarely black with white markings. The surface is smooth, with black feathery setae covering the markings. There are several long curved setae on the clypeus, eye region and posterior to the posterior eye row up to mid-point. The carapace is oval, broadest at the posterior of coxae II and the eye region is narrow. The fovea is distinct; the posterior margin very slightly concave or straight. The oval abdomen is either yellow-orange with black markings or black with white markings. There are three pairs of fine straight setae on the anterior margin above the pedicel. The dorsal scutum is small, strongly sclerotised, extending less than an eighth of the abdomen length in females and slightly more than half of the abdomen length in males.

LIFESTYLE: *Copa* are predominantly ground-living and commonly found in the leaf litter of various habitats and are occurring widely in savanna woodlands but also occasionally in forests. They are well camouflaged and closely resemble wolf spiders (Lycosidae) in general appearance. They are very fast runners, and often hide below leaves on the ground when coming to a halt. Egg sacs are about 10 mm in diameter, have a papery yellow-brown appearance, and are constructed inside curled dead leaves on the ground.

TAXONOMY: The continental African species of the genus *Copa* were revised by Haddad (2013b).

Figures 1–2. *Copa flavoplumosa*, female habitus in anterior (1) and dorsal (2) views. Photo credits: 1 Peter Webb. 2 Charles Haddad.

Copa flavoplumosa Simon, 1885

COMMON NAME: African ground lycosiform sac spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1885 from Angola. It has been collected from many countries throughout the Afrotropical Region. In South Africa, it is known from all nine provinces, including >10 protected areas (EOO = 813 478 km²; AOO = 244 km²; 6–2102 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Widely distributed throughout the Afrotropical Region.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Great Fish River Wetland Park, Selbourne (-33.48, 27.13); Mkambati Nature Reserve. -31.31, 29.96); Sterkstroom. -31.55, 26.54); Sundays River Valley, near Kirkwood (-33.39, 25.43). **Free State:** Clocolan, Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.80, 27.65); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.50, 26.80); Sandveld Nature Reserve (-27.85, 25.93). **Gauteng:** Alice Glockner Nature Reserve, Farm Houtpoort (-26.56, 28.37); Balmoral (-25.80, 28.74); Pretoria National Botanical Garden (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria/Tshwane, Buffelsdrift (-25.40, 28.06); Pretoria/Tshwane, Weavind Park (-25.74, 28.19); Irene, field opposite Gem Village (-25.89, 28.23). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Cathedral Peak (-28.94, 29.19); Enseleni Nature Reserve (-28.68, 32.05); Garden Castle (-29.75, 29.20); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Hell's Gate (-28.00, 32.48); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Mkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.40, 32.76); Ithala Nature Reserve, Ngubhu Loop (-27.51, 31.23); Louwsburg (-27.54, 31.32); Midlands (-29.25, 30.34); Mkhuzi Game Reserve (-27.60, 32.02); Mount Edgecombe, Illovo Beach (-29.68, 31.03); Ndumo Game Reserve, Banzi Pan (-26.54, 32.15); Ndumo Game Reserve, Crocodile Farm (-26.90, 32.32); Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); 15 km N of Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.10); Sani Pass (-29.62, 29.37); Sani Pass 1500 m alt (-29.66, 29.46); Sani Pass 1800 m alt. (-29.68, 29.51); Sani Pass 2100 m alt. (-29.62, 29.44); Tembe Elephant Park (-27.03, 32.42). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Entabeni Nature Reserve (-22.992, 30.2570); Lajuma Mountain Retreat (-23.04, 29.45); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.04, 29.44); Makgabeng area, W of Senwabawana (-23.24, 28.85); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Pafuri, Waller's Camp (-22.42, 30.91); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.90, 29.47); Tuinplaas, Springbokvlakte (-24.90, 28.73); Venetia, Limpopo Valley Reserve (-22.32, 29.32); Western Soutpansberg, Farm Little Leigh (-22.95, 29.86). **Mpumalanga:** 20 km NE of Brondal (-25.35, 30.84); Dullstroom, Farm

Figures 1–9. *Copa flavoplumosa*. 1, 2. Female habitus. 3. Subadult male habitus. 4, 5, 8. Epigyne, ventral view. 6, 7, 9. Same, dorsal view. Photo credits: 1, 2, 4–7 Charles Haddad. 3 Rudolph Steenkamp. 8, 9 From Haddad (2013b).

Copa flavoplumosa Simon, 1885

Biennial (-25.53, 30.10); Dullstroom, Groblers Farm (-25.48, 30.08); Dullstroom, Sakhelwe Communal land (-25.40, 30.08); Groblersdal (-25.16, 29.39); Hectorspruit, Farm Vergelegen (-25.43, 31.68); Kruger National Park, Skukuza Camp (-24.99, 31.59); Lydenburg, Farm Rodewalshoek (-25.22, 30.40); Nelspruit, Lowveld National Botanical Gardens (-25.47, 31.00). **Mpumalanga:** Marble Hall, Schoeman Farms (-24.96, 29.29); Nelspruit Agricultural College (-25.34, 31.77); Roodebank (-26.64, 29.01); Verloren Vallei Nature Reserve (-25.53, 30.13); Witbank Dam Nature Reserve (-25.86, 29.30). **North West:** Matshaneng, Farm Hermitage (-20.97, 31.65); Venterskroon, Thabela Thabeng Mountain Retreat (-27.08, 28.51). **Northern Cape:** Kuruman, Farm Sunnyside (-25.65, 27.22); Prieska, Farm Green Valley Nuts (-29.68, 22.74). **Western Cape:** De Hoop Nature Reserve, Koppie Alleen (-34.29, 20.29).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground-dweller mainly collected from the leaf litter layer of all of the main Biome types in Africa, except for true deserts and Karoo habitats. The species was also sampled from crops such as avocado, citrus, macadamia, pistachio orchards and strawberries, cotton and maize fields.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is recorded from several protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Haddad (2013b). Known from both sexes.

Figures 1–6. *Copa flavoplumosa*. 1. Male habitus. 2, 4. Male palp, ventral view. 3, 5. Same, retro-lateral view. 6. Embolus. Photo credits: 1–3. Charles Haddad. 4–6. From Haddad (2013b).

Copa kei Haddad, 2013

COMMON NAME: Kei ground lycosiform sac spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic known from two provinces, including three protected areas (EOO = 43 165 km²; AOO = 40 km²; 7–1505 m a.s.l.). Although threatened by loss of habitat for urbanization and agricultural activities in parts of its range, it is well protected in other areas. Due to its wide geographic range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Cwebe Nature Reserve, The Haven (-32.20, 28.90); Dwesa Nature Reserve (-32.27, 28.87); East London Pineapple Research Station (-33.01, 27.90); Hogsback (-32.59, 26.92); Katberg (-32.78, 26.62); Kei Mouth (-32.68, 28.30); Lusikisiki district, Mzimhlava River mouth (-31.37, 29.58). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Howick (-29.47, 30.20); Karkloof Nature Reserve (-29.25, 30.34); Pietermaritzburg, Town Bush (-29.60, 30.38).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living ground-dweller mainly collected from the leaf litter layer in Afromontane and coastal forests in the Forest, Savanna and Thicket biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species but it is threatened by loss of habitat for infrastructure development near Pietermaritzburg and crop farming around Mzimhlava River near Lusikisiki. It is recorded from several protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Haddad, 2013b).

Figures 1–9. *Copa kei*. 1. Male habitus. 2, 4. Male palp, ventral view. 3, 5. Same, retrolateral view. 6–8. Epigyne, ventral view. 9. Same, dorsal view. Photo credits: 1, 2, 3, 6, 7 Charles Haddad. 4, 5, 8, 9 From Haddad (2013b).

GENUS *COPUETTA* Haddad, 2013

The genus *Copuetta* is known from 13 species, of which five are known from South Africa.

COMMON NAME: Tree lycosiform sac spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Copuetta maputa* Haddad, 2013

MORPHOLOGY: These medium to large spiders have a smooth carapace with black feathery setae forming different markings. There are several long curved setae on the clypeus and the posterior eye row is slightly procurved. There are only two pairs of ventral spines on the anterior tibiae.

LIFESTYLE: The spiders were sampled from a variety of habitats and found from ground level to the tree canopy. Some species are synanthropic and collected in and around houses at night.

TAXONOMY: Genus described by Haddad (2013c).

Figures 1–2. 1. *Copuetta lacustris*, female habitus. 2. *Copuetta* sp., subadult female of undescribed species. Photo credits: Charles Haddad.

Copuetta erecta Haddad, 2013

COMMON NAME: Dwarf tree lycosiform sac spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 2013 from Tembe Elephant Park, South Africa. Also known from Mozambique. In South Africa, the species has only been recorded from KwaZulu-Natal, including several protected areas (EOO = 116 674 km²; AOO = 32 km²; 18–1427 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mozambique and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: KwaZulu-Natal: iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.40, 32.76); iSimangaliso Wetlands Park, False Bay Park (-27.92, 32.27); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Hell's Gate (-29.29, 26.27); Ndumo Game Reserve, Pongola River (-27.33, 31.45); Port Shepstone (-30.74, 30.44); Ramsgate, Butterfly Sanctuary (-30.88, 30.34); Tembe Elephant Park (-27.03, 32.42); Umlazi Nature Reserve (-28.96, 31.76).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living spider sampled by sifting leaf litter, beating and canopy fogging in closed-canopied coastal dune forests, riverine forests and savanna habitats in the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is recorded from several protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Haddad, 2013c).

Figures 1–6. *Copuetta erecta*. 1. Female habitus. 2. Male habitus. 3. Male palp, ventral view. 4. Same, retrolateral view. 5. Epigyne, ventral view. 6. Same, dorsal view. Photo credits: 1, 2 Charles Haddad. 3–6. From Haddad (2013c).

Copuetta lacustris (Strand, 1916)

COMMON NAME: African tree lycosiform sac spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described from the Democratic Republic of the Congo as *Copa lacustris*. It is known from numerous countries in Central, East and southern Africa. In South Africa, it is known from all nine provinces, including several protected areas (EOO = 703 034 km²; AOO = 148 km²; 4–1676 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Central, East and Southern Africa: Botswana, eSwatini, Lesotho, Mozambique, Zimbabwe and South Africa (all nine provinces).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Middelburg (-31.49, 24.99). **Free State:** Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.60, 26.43); Bloemfontein (-29.13, 26.17); Bloemfontein, Free State National Botanical Gardens (-29.05, 26.21); Bloemfontein, Farm Deelhoek (-28.85, 26.12); Bloemfontein, Maselspoort (-29.03, 26.41); Bloemfontein, Farm Hopefield (-28.90, 26.23); Clocolan, Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.80, 25.72); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.50, 26.79); Harrismith (-28.28, 29.11); Kroonstad, Farm Koffielaagte (-27.48, 27.47); Petrusburg, Farm Driekoppies (-29.14, 25.61); Sandveld Nature Reserve (-27.85, 25.93); Smithfield (-30.20, 26.53); Virginia (-28.12, 26.75); Winburg, Allemanskraal Dam (-28.27, 27.17). **Gauteng:** Johannesburg, Sandton (-26.11, 28.05); Kempton Park (-26.09, 28.23); Pretoria/Tshwane, Monument Park (-25.81, 28.24); Winterness (-25.65, 28.13); Roodeplaat Research Station (-25.66, 28.35). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Empangeni (-28.75, 31.90); KwaDlangezwa (-28.75, 31.75); Illovo Beach (-30.11, 30.85); Mount Edgecombe (-30.12, 30.85); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Pietermaritzburg (-29.55, 30.35). **Limpopo:** Bela-Bela (-24.88, 28.29); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Farm Malta (-24.16, 30.25); Settlers (-24.95, 28.52); Springbok Flats, Tuinplaas (-24.56, 28.46). **Mpumulanga:** Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96); Nelspruit, Lowveld National Botanical Gardens (-25.47, 31.00). **Northern Cape:** Red Sands Country Lodge, 14 km SW of Kuruman (-27.51, 23.29). **North West:** Bloemhof (-27.65, 25.60); Potchefstroom, Mooivalleipark (-27.17, 27.15); Venterkroon, Thabela Thabeng Mountain Retreat (-27.08, 28.51). **Western Cape:** Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Knysna, Uitzicht Annex (-34.00, 23.33); Oudtshoorn (-33.59, 22.21); Worcester (-33.64, 19.47); Rawsonville (-33.70, 19.34).

Figures 1–3. *Copuetta lacustris* females. Photo credits: 1, 2 Peter Webb. 3 Charles Haddad.

Copuetta lacustris (continued)

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living spider sampled from a wide range of habitats and is found from ground level to the tree canopy. Frequently collected in urban areas, where it is often seen inside houses at night, especially during spring. Their egg sacs are approximately 8 mm in diameter and constructed under bark in natural habitats and under window sills, door frames and on wooden structures in and around houses. Sampled from the Grassland, Nama Karoo, Forest, Fynbos and Savanna biomes. Also sampled from pistachio orchards, maize fields and vineyards.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It has been recorded from several protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Redescribed by Haddad (2013c). Known from both sexes.

Figures 1–10. *Copuetta lacustris*. 1, 4. Male palp, ventral view. 2, 5. Same, retrolateral view. 3. Embolus. 6. Male habitus. 7, 9. Epigyne, ventral view. 8, 10. Same, dorsal view. Photo credits: 1–3, 6, 7, 9. Charles Haddad. 4, 5, 8, 10 From Haddad (2013c).

Copuetta lotzi Haddad, 2013

COMMON NAME: Lotz's tree lycosiform sac spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 2013 from Bloemfontein in the Free State. Sampled from four provinces and protected in four protected areas (EOO = 94 482 km²; AOO = 44 km²; 613–1601 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Benfontein Game Reserve (-28.85, 24.88); Bloemfontein, Farm Deelhoek (-28.83, 26.08); Bloemfontein, Free State National Botanical Gardens (-29.05, 26.21); Bloemfontein, Langenhoven Park (-29.11, 26.22); Bloemfontein, Naval Hill (-28.09, 26.23); Brandfort, Florisbad Research Station (-28.77, 26.07); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.50, 26.80); Tussen-die-Riviere Nature Reserve (-30.47, 25.19). **Gauteng:** Balmoral (-25.85, 28.96); Randburg, Glen Austin Pan, Farm Randjesfontein (-25.97, 28.17). **Mpumulanga:** Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46). **Western Cape:** Anysberg Nature Reserve, Landsekloof (-33.53, 20.76).

LIFESTYLE: Ground-dwellers occurring in the more arid Grassland and Nama Karoo biomes of South Africa. Sampled with pittraps but also from under bark and rocks, and found inside abandoned *Trinervitermes trinervoides* termite mounds. Occasionally found in houses, but not as frequently as *C. lacustris*.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is recorded from several protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Haddad, 2013c).

Figures 1–11. *Copuetta lotzi*. 1. Male habitus. 2. Female habitus. 3, 8. Male palp, ventral view. 4, 9. Same, retrolateral view. 5. Embolus. 6, 10. Epigyne, ventral view. 7, 11. Same, dorsal view. Photo credits: 1–7 Charles Haddad. 8–11 From Haddad (2013c).

Copuetta magna Haddad, 2013

COMMON NAME: Giant tree lycosiform sac spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 2013 from Ndumo Game Reserve, South Africa. Also sampled from Mozambique and Tanzania. The species is known from three provinces, including four protected areas (EOO = 65 786 km²; AOO = 32 km²; 4–1303 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mozambique, Tanzania and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **KwaZulu-Natal:** Hattingspruit (-28.08, 30.13); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, False Bay (-27.92, 32.27); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Hell's Gate (-28.20, 32.43); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); Ndumo Game Reserve, Ezulwini Hide (-26.91, 32.28); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.41, 31.39). **Mpumalanga:** Hazyview, Farm Brandwag (-25.03, 31.12); Kruger National Park, Skukuza (-24.95, 31.67). **Limpopo:** Hoedspruit (-24.35, 30.97).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-living spider collected from tsetse fly traps, walls of houses, tree bark and tree canopies in the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is recorded from several protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Haddad, 2013c).

Figures 1–10. *Copuetta magna*. 1, 2. Female habitus. 3, 7. Male palp, ventral view. 4, 8. Same, retro-lateral view. 5, 9. Epigyne, ventral view. 6, 10. Same, dorsal view. Photo credits: 1, 3–6 Charles Haddad. 2 Stanislav Snäll. 7–10 From Haddad (2013c).

Copuetta maputa Haddad, 2013

COMMON NAME: Maputaland tree lycosiform sac spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 2013 from Ndumo Game Reserve, South Africa. The species was also sampled from Mozambique. In South Africa, it has been sampled from several areas in KwaZulu-Natal and is conserved in two protected areas (EOO = 4190 km²; AOO = 24 km²; 6–96 m a.s.l.). Throughout its range, it has only been collected along the Maputaland coastal plain at elevations lower than 100 m a.s.l.. Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mozambique and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: KwaZulu-Natal: iSimangaliso Wetlands Park, Crocodile Centre (-28.36, 32.42); iSimangaliso Wetlands Park, False Bay Park (-27.92, 32.27); iSimangaliso Wetlands Park, Hell's Gate (-28.00, 32.48); iSimangaliso Wetlands Park, Lake Sibaya (-27.33, 32.68); iSimangaliso Wetlands Park, Sodwana Bay to Lake Sibaya (-27.42, 32.71); Ndumo Game Reserve, Crocodile Farm (-26.91, 32.32); Ndumo Game Reserve, Shokwe Pan (-26.88, 32.21).

LIFESTYLE: Collected in various strata of forest and woodland habitats (shrubs, tree bark, tree canopies and leaf litter) in the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes. Also collected from the walls of houses.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It has been recorded from several protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Haddad, 2013c).

Figures 1–7. *Copuetta maputa*. 1. Female habitus. 2. Male habitus. 3. Male palpal embolus. 4. Male palpal, ventral view. 5. Same, retrolateral view. 6. Epigyne, ventral view. 7. Same, dorsal view. Photo credits: 1–3 Charles Haddad. 4–7 From Haddad (2013c).

GENUS *CORINNOMMA* Karsch, 1880

The genus *Corinnomma* is represented by 14 species, with most of them described from southern and eastern Asia. Three species are known from Africa, of which two have been recorded from South Africa.

COMMON NAME: Banded ant-like sac spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Corinna severa* Thorell, 1877

MORPHOLOGY: These medium-sized spiders have elongate-oval carapaces with globose abdomens and a sclerotized petiole. The eyes are small and arranged in a slightly recurved posterior eye row. Abdominal markings are distinct and resemble ant bodies.

LIFESTYLE: They are ground-dwellers that mimic ants, occasionally wandering onto low-growing foliage.

TAXONOMY: Two species are known from South Africa (Haddad, 2006).

Figures 1–2. *Corinnomma semiglabrum* females, habitus. Photo credits: 1 Ruan Booyesen. 2 Rudolph Steenkamp.

Corinnomma lawrencei Haddad, 2006

COMMON NAME: Lawrence's banded ant-like sac spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 2006 from Mozambique. The species is also known from four African countries. In South Africa, it is known from two provinces, including three protected areas (EOO = 96 994 km²; AOO = 24km²; 47–1411 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Tanzania, Mozambique, Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Ndumo Game Reserve, Crocodile Farm (-26.87, 32.24). *Limpopo:* Kruger National Park, Ndengeza (-23.32, 30.41); Kruger National Park, Pafuri (-22.33, 31.17); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Lephhalale/Ellisras (-23.67, 27.71); Vyeboom (-23.14, 30.38).

LIFESTYLE: This ant-mimicking species is a ground-dweller that is usually collected from leaf litter and is often found near nests of *Camponotus cinctellus* and *Anoplolepis custodiens* ants in the Savanna Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It has been recorded from several protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Haddad, 2006).

Figures 1–6. *Corinnomma lawrencei*. 1. Female habitus. 2. Male palpal embolus. 3. Male palp, ventral view. 4. Same, retrolateral view. 5. Epigyne, ventral view. 6. Same, dorsal view. Photo credits: 1 Charles Haddad. 2–6 From Haddad (2006).

Corinnomma semiglabrum (Simon, 1896)

COMMON NAME: Common banded ant-like sac spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1896 as *Apochinomma semiglabrum* from Makapan in the Limpopo Province. The species is also known from six African countries. In South Africa, it is known from five provinces, including six protected areas (EOO = 266 869 km²; AOO = 88 km²; 6–1762 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Zambia, Swaziland, Mozambique, Namibia, Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Bronkhorstspuit (-25.80, 28.74); Crocodile River, Hartebeespoortdam (-25.73, 27.85); Johannesburg, Florida (-26.20, 28.04); Pretoria/Tshwane, Wonderboom (-25.65, 28.65). **KwaZulu-Natal:** iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Hell's Gate (-28.00, 32.48); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Zululand, Lewombo Mission Station (-28.33, 32.00). **Limpopo:** Gunfontein (-24.00, 28.00); Klein Kariba (-24.88, 28.29); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.038, 29.442); Mabula Nature Reserve (-24.84, 27.96); Makapan (-24.15, 29.18); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Settlers (-24.95, 28.52); Tuinplaas, Springbokvlakte (-24.56, 28.46); Wolkberg Nature Reserve (-23.94, 29.95). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park, Skukuza Camp (-24.99, 31.59); Marble Hall, Wolwekraal (-24.96, 29.29). **North West:** Brits, Silkaatsnek (-25.70, 27.89); Hartbeespoortdam, Crocodile River (-25.73, 27.85); Rustenburg, Kroondal (-25.75, 27.32); Vryburg, Farm Weltevrede (-27.41, 24.51).

LIFESTYLE: The ant-mimicking species is mainly collected in pitfall traps or leaf litter, indicating that this is a primarily epigeic species. Sampled from the Grassland, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes. It was also sampled from citrus orchards.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is recorded from several protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Haddad (2006). Known from both sexes.

Figures 1–7. *Corinnomma semiglabrum*. 1, 2. Female habitus. 3. Male palpal embolus. 4. Male palp, ventral view. 5. Same, retrolateral view. 6. Epigyne, ventral view. 7. Same, dorsal view. Photo credits: 1. Charles Haddad. 2. Rudolph Steenkamp. 3–7. From Haddad (2006).

GENUS *ECHINAX* Deeleman-Reinhold, 2001

The genus *Echinax* is represented by 13 species, of which seven are from Africa and two from South Africa.

COMMON NAME: Pale lycosiform sac spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Echinax oxyopoides* (Deeleman-Reinhold, 1995)

MORPHOLOGY: *Echinax* resembles *Copa* and *Copuetta* in their general body shape, heavily spined legs and the presence of cryptic colouration that resembles wolf spiders. They can be distinguished by their smaller size (< 6 mm), the presence of very long leg spines distally on all of the patellae and the long spines on the anterior metatarsi, and by their paler colouration. The anterior median eyes are two to three times the size of the anterior lateral eyes.

LIFESTYLE: *Echinax* is found in the foliage of shrubs and trees and two species are known from South Africa. The available ecological data indicates that all seven African species are mainly arboreal and represent a prominent component of corinnid assemblage collected by canopy fogging, especially in forests.

TAXONOMY: The genus was revised by Haddad (2012b).

Figures 1–2. *Echinax natalensis*. 1. Female carapace and eye region. 2. Legs I and II, showing the long leg spines on the patellae and tibiae. Photo credits: Charles Haddad.

Echinax natalensis Haddad, 2012

COMMON NAME: Natal pale lycosiform sac spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic species described in 2012 from the iSimangaliso Wetland Park. The species is known from two provinces and is conserved in several protected areas (EOO = 44 493 km²; AOO = 28 km²; 4–381 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species, and due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Mount Coke State Forest (-32.99, 27.48). *KwaZulu-Natal:* iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Cape Vidal (-28.16, 32.56); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Fanie's Island (-28.10, 32.45); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Hell's Gate (-28.02, 32.26); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, St. Lucia (-28.36, 32.41); Ndumo Game Reserve, Pongola River (-26.91, 32.32).

LIFESTYLE: The species was collected from tsetse fly traps set up in coastal forest, canopy fogging and beating of trees in riparian forest and savanna habitats in the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It has been recorded from several protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Haddad, 2012b).

Figures 1–11. *Echinax natalensis*. 1. Subadult male habitus. 2. Female habitus. 3. Male habitus. 4, 9. Male palp, ventral view. 5, 10. Same, retrolateral view. 6. Male palpal embolus. 11. Epigyne, ventral view. Photo credits: 1, 4, 5, 7, 8 Charles Haddad. 2, 3, 6, 9–11 From Haddad (2012b).

Echinax similis Haddad, 2012

COMMON NAME: Ndumo pale lycosiform sac spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described in 2012 from Ndumo Game Reserve. The species is known only from the type locality (EOO = <math><100\text{ km}^2</math>; AOO =

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal*: Ndumo Game Reserve, Shokwe Pan (-26.88, 32.21).

LIFESTYLE: The species was collected by canopy fogging from three broad-leaved tree species in seasonally inundated *Ficus sycomorus* forest in the Savanna Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Haddad, 2012b).

Figures 1–11. *Echinax similis*. 1. Female habitus. 2. Male habitus. 3, 8. Male palp, ventral view. 4, 9. Same, retrolateral view. 6. Male palpal embolus. 6, 10. Epigyne, ventral view. 7, 11. Same, dorsal view. Photo credits: 1, 2, 5, 8–11 From Haddad (2012b). 3, 4, 6, 7 Charles Haddad.

GENUS *GRAPTARTIA* Simon, 1896

The genus *Graptartia* is represented by two species.

COMMON NAME: Four-spotted mutilliform sac spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Graptartia granulosa* Simon, 1896

MORPHOLOGY: Carapace is uniformly deep orange, red or purple; evenly high, slightly elevated towards rear; highest at two-thirds its length; surface granular, especially at setal bases; short and long white setae scattered across surface. Abdomen is oval with large dorsal scutum; dorsum pitted, with blackened undertone; two pairs of large, white spots dorsally, composed of white clavate setae. Legs with scattered feathery setae.

LIFESTYLE: This genus is known to mimic velvet ants.

TAXONOMY: Revised by Haddad (2004).

Figures 1–2. *Graptartia granulosa*. 1. Male. 2. Female. Photo credits: 1 Ruan Booysen. 2 Ian Riddell.

Graptartia granulosa Simon, 1896

COMMON NAME: Four-spotted mutilliform sac spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1896, with the type locality given as Zambezi. The species is known from ten African countries. Material was only sampled from South Africa after the Haddad (2004) revision. In South Africa, the species is presently known from localities in the Limpopo and KwaZulu-Natal provinces (EOO = 81 370 km²; AOO = 20 km²; 286–1217 m a.s.l.). There are no significant known threats to the species. Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Kenya, Malawi, Mozambique, Namibia, Tanzania, Zambia, Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Ndumo Game Reserve, Nyamiti Pan (-26.89, 32.31). *Limpopo:* Kruger National Park, Nyandu sandveld (-22.93, 31.02); Kruger National Park, Shingwedzi (-23.12, 31.43); Tshulu Camp (-22.58, 30.81); Waterberg, Melkrivier (-23.98, 28.39).

LIFESTYLE: This ground-dwelling mimic of velvet ants is known from a variety of habitats, but appears to prefer the Savanna Biome, where it is usually collected in pitfall traps and leaf litter, or under prone objects, where it shelters when not active.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Haddad (2004). Known from both sexes.

Figures 1–9. *Graptartia granulosa*. 1–3. Male habitus. 4, 6. Male palp, ventral view. 5, 7. Same, retro-lateral view. 8. Epigyne, ventral view. 9. Same, dorsal view. Photo credits: 1, 2 Rudolph Steenkamp. 3–5 Charles Haddad. 6–9 From Haddad (2004).

GENUS *HORTIPES* Bosselaers & Ledoux, 1998

Hortipes is an endemic Afrotropical spider genus, and is also one of the most species-rich genera on the continent (70 spp.). South Africa is one of the biodiversity hotspots for the genus, with 14 species described from the country.

COMMON NAME: Basket-legged spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Hortipes luytenae* Bosselaers & Ledoux, 1998

MORPHOLOGY: This genus is recognized by the large anterior median eyes and the strange arrangement of setae dorsally on metatarsi I and II. They are small yellow to orange spiders and the metatarsi of legs I and II are provided with three pairs of spines ventrally. Their carapace is raised posteriorly with a strong posterior slope. The eyes are small except for the anterior median eyes that are large. The posterior eye row is recurved. They are widely distributed throughout Africa and seem to be more common in forest areas. Fourteen species are known from South Africa.

LIFESTYLE: *Hortipes* are tiny leaf litter-dwelling spiders that can be easily recognized by their stout bodies and bright yellow, orange or pink colouration. They are usually found in high-moisture forests, wetlands and savanna habitats, predominantly in the Savanna, Forest, Thicket and Indian Ocean Coastal Belt biomes. They are conspicuously absent from grasslands, Nama and Succulent Karoo and fynbos habitats.

TAXONOMY: The genus was described by Bosselaers & Ledoux (1998) and revised by Bosselaers & Jocqué (2000), but there have been no subsequent taxonomic treatments on this mysterious genus aside from the description of a single species from West Africa.

Figures 1–6. *Hortipes messembrinus* (1–4) and *Hortipes* sp. (5–6). 1. Female habitus. 2, 5. Female eye pattern. 3, 4, 6. Modified arrangement of setae on metatarsus I and II, resembling a basket. Photo credits: 1–4 Charles Haddad. 5, 6 From Bosselaers & Ledoux (1998).

Hortipes aelurisiepae Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000

COMMON NAME: Ingwavuma basket-legged spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 2000 from Ingwavuma in northern KwaZulu-Natal. The species is also known from Mozambique, but may possibly be under-collected. In South Africa, it is only known from KwaZulu-Natal, where it is conserved in three protected areas (EOO = 1726 km²; AOO = 16 km²; 30–646 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range in southern Africa it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mozambique and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: KwaZulu-Natal: Ingwavuma, Gualiveni Forest (-27.12, 32.01); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.40, 32.76); Ndumo Game Reserve, Pongola River (-26.89, 32.32); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47).

LIFESTYLE: Small free-running humus spiders, with some specimens sampled from forest areas. Sampled from the Forest, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is recorded from several protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female (Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000). However, this species was collected together with the males of *H. griswoldi* at Ndumo Game Reserve, so it is likely that the two species are synonyms.

Figures 1–2. *Hortipes aelurisiepae*. 1. Epigyne, ventral view. 2. Same, dorsal view. From Bosselaers & Jocqué (2000).

Hortipes atalante Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000

COMMON NAME: Umgeni basket-legged spider

NATIONAL STATUS: VU

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described in 2000 from Umgeni River, Lions River District. The species is also known from three protected areas: Ithala Game Reserve, Krantzkloof Nature Reserve and Umgeni Valley Nature Reserve (EOO = 8083 km²; AOO = 12 km²; 475–1243 m a.s.l.). Due to the species having a small distribution range (< 20 000 km²), it is regarded as Vulnerable.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: KwaZulu-Natal: Ithala Game Reserve (-27.51, 31.23); Krantzkloof Nature Reserve (-29.77, 30.83); Umgeni Valley Nature Reserve (-29.42, 30.22).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a small free-running humus spider, collected from under bushes along river banks from the Savanna Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling is needed to collect the male and determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female.

Figures 1–2. *Hortipes atalante*. 1. Epigyne, ventral view. 2. Same, dorsal view. From Bosselaers & Jocqué (2000).

Hortipes coccinatus Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000

COMMON NAME: Limpopo basket-legged spider

NATIONAL STATUS: VU

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Limpopo endemic described in 2000 from Woodbush Forest, Pietersburg/Polokwane, Limpopo. The species is known from two protected areas: Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve and Woodbush Forest Reserve (EOO = 1579 km²; AOO = 24 km²; 920–1500 m a.s.l.). Although it is threatened by agricultural activities in parts of its range, it is protected in two reserves and several forests in and around Tzaneen. Due to the species having a small restricted distribution range (<5 000 km²), it is listed as Vulnerable.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: 6 km E of Haenertsburg, Farm B11 (-23.95, 29.93); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-24.17, 30.25); Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87); Magoebaskloof Forest, Farm Hideaway (-23.84, 30.04); Pietersburg/ Polokwane (-23.89, 29.46).

LIFESTYLE: This species is strongly associated with leaf litter in woodland habitats in the Forest and Savanna biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is threatened by loss of habitat for crop farming around Haenertsburg.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000).

Figures 1–5. *Hortipes coccinatus*. 1. Female habitus. 2. Male palp, ventral view. 3. Same, retrolateral view. 4. Epigyne, ventral view. 5. Same, dorsal view. Photo credits: 1 Peter Webb. 2–5 From Bosselaers & Jocqué (2000).

Hortipes contubernalis Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000

COMMON NAME: Entebeni basket-legged spider

NATIONAL STATUS: Rare.

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Limpopo endemic described in 2000 from Entabeni Forest. It is known from three localities in Limpopo and protected in the Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (EOO = 100 km²; AOO = 12 km²; 969–1339 m a.s.l.). There are no known significant threats to the species. Due to the species having a small restricted distribution range (<500 km²) it is regarded as Rare.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Entabeni State Forest (-23.00, 30.25); Hanglip Forest (-23.04, 29.91); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.04, 29.45).

LIFESTYLE: This species is strongly associated with leaf litter in woodland habitats. It has been recorded from the Forest and Savanna biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are some farming activities around two of the localities, but there are some patches of indigenous forest that the species could still inhabit and thrive in.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000).

Figures 1–5. *Hortipes contubernalis*. 1. Female habitus. 2. Male palp, ventral view. 3. Same, retro-lateral view. 4. Epigyne, ventral view. 5. Same, dorsal view. Photo credits: 1 Hans Henderickx. 2–5 From Bosselaers & Jocqué (2000).

Hortipes griswoldi Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000

COMMON NAME: Griswold's basket-legged spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 2000 from Ceylon Forest, at Sabie in Mpumalanga. It is known from only two provinces and is protected in the Ndumo Game Reserve (EOO = <1000 km²; AOO = 8 km²; 30–1050 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range and evaluate whether it represents the undescribed male of *H. aelurisiopae*. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.80, 32.32). *Mpumalanga:* Sabie, Ceylon Forest (-25.10, 30.78).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-running ground-dweller known from leaf litter in indigenous forests and floodplains in the Forest and Savanna biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female (Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000).

Figures 1–2. *Hortipes griswoldi*. 1. Male palp, ventral view. 2. Same, retrolateral view. From Bosselaers & Jocqué (2000).

Hortipes hyakutake Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000

COMMON NAME: Ingogo basket-legged spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described in 2000, known only from the type locality, Ingogo Forest Reserve (EOO = <100 km²; AOO = 4 km²; 244 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species' range. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape: Msikaba, Ingogo Forest Reserve (-31.28, 29.90).

LIFESTYLE: This species is strongly associated with leaf litter in woodland habitats in the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species is threatened by loss of habitat for farming activities and infrastructure development.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the male (Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000).

Figures 1–2. *Hortipes hyakutake*. 1. Male palp, ventral view. 2. Same, retrolateral view. From Bosselaers & Jocqué (2000).

Hortipes irimus Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000

COMMON NAME: Port Shepstone basket-legged spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described in 2000, and only known from the type locality, Port Shepstone (EOO = 4 km²; AOO = 4 km²; 1 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal*: Port Shepstone (-30.74, 30.45).

LIFESTYLE: This species is strongly associated with leaf litter in coastal woodland habitats. It is a free-living ground-dweller known from the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt in southern KwaZulu-Natal.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species is threatened by loss of habitat due to urbanization around Port Shepstone.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female (Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000).

Figures 1–2. *Hortipes irimus*. 1. Epigyne, ventral view. 2. Same, dorsal view. From Bosselaers & Jocqué (2000).

Hortipes lincophorus Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000

COMMON NAME: Mariepskop basket-legged spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Mpumalanga endemic described in 2000 and known only from the type locality, Mariepskop Forest (EOO = 4 km²; AOO = 4 km²; 1431 m a.s.l.). Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Mpumalanga*: Mariepskop (-24.56, 30.88).

LIFESTYLE: This species strongly associated with leaf litter in forest habitats. It is known from the Northern Escarpment Quartzite Sourveld in the Savanna Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female (Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000).

Figures 1–2. *Hortipes lincophorus*. 1. Epigyne, ventral view. 2. Same, dorsal view. From Bosselaers & Jocqué (2000).

Hortipes luytenae Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000

COMMON NAME: Ngome basket-legged spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described in 1998 and known only from the type locality, Ngome State Forest (EOO = <100 km²; AOO = 4 km²; 1044 m a.s.l.). They were quite common and >170 specimens were sampled from the type locality with pitfall traps (Van der Merwe *et al.*, 1996). There are no known threats to the species. More sampling is needed to determine the species' range. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal*: Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45).

LIFESTYLE: This species is strongly associated with leaf litter in forest habitats. A total of 106 males and 73 females were collected in pitfall traps in forested areas in Ngome State Forest, a Southern Mistbelt Forest in the Savanna Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species and it is protected in a state forest.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Redescribed by Bosselaers & Jocqué (2000). Known from both sexes.

Figures 1–4. *Hortipes luytenae*. 1. Male palp, ventral view. 2. Same, retrolateral view. 3. Epigyne, ventral view. 4. Same, dorsal view. From Bosselaers & Jocqué (2000).

Hortipes merwei Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000

COMMON NAME: Van der Merwe's basket-legged spider

NATIONAL STATUS: VU

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described in 2000 from Ngome State Forest. The species is relatively widespread in northern KwaZulu-Natal and is quite common in litter samples. It is known from several localities, including three protected areas: iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Ngome State Forest and Ophathe Game Reserve (EOO = 11 831 km²; AOO = 28 km²; 4–1061 m a.s.l.). It may still be undersampled and is expected to be relatively widespread in northern KwaZulu-Natal. Due to the species having a small distribution range (<20 000 km²), it is regarded as Vulnerable.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: KwaZulu-Natal: Dukuduku Forest Station (-28.34, 32.40); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Eastern Shores Nature Reserve (-29.10, 32.16); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Fanie's Island (-28.11, 32.44); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Lake St. Lucia (-27.64, 32.58); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Mission Rocks Picnic Site (-28.26, 32.48); Ngome State Forest (-27.87, 31.03); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.41, 31.39).

LIFESTYLE: This species is strongly associated with leaf litter in woodland and forest habitats. It is known from Southern Mistbelt Forest and woodlands in the Forest, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes. Also sampled from commercial pine plantations.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species is threatened by habitat loss for agricultural activities, silviculture and degradation around Lake St. Lucia.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000).

Figures 1–5. *Hortipes merwei*. 1. Female habitus. 2. Male palp, ventral view. 3. Same, retrolateral view. 4. Epigyne, ventral view. 5. Same, dorsal view. Photo credits: 1 Hans Henderickx. 2–5 From Bosselaers & Jocqué (2000).

Hortipes mesembrinus Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000

COMMON NAME: Eastern Cape basket-legged spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described in 2000 from East London. The species is known from several localities, including two protected areas: Cwebe Nature Reserve and Mount Coke State Forest (EOO = 4568 km²; AOO = 52 km²; 1–789 m a.s.l.). The male has been collected but has not yet been described, but further collecting is necessary to determine the species' range. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Coffee Bay (-31.59, 29.09); Cwebe Nature Reserve, The Haven (-32.15, 28.55); East London, Pineapple Research Station (-33.01, 27.90); Kei Mouth (-32.68, 28.37); Mazeppa Bay (-32.27, 28.37); Mount Coke State Forest (-32.99, 27.48).

LIFESTYLE: The species is known from leaf litter in woodlands and coastal forests from Ngongoni Veld, Bhisho Thornveld, Transkei Coastal Belt and Albany Coastal Belt in the Forest, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species is threatened by habitat loss due to urbanization around East London and Kei Mouth, and agricultural activities near Mazeppa Bay and Coffee Bay.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female (Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000). The male has been sampled (Figures 3, 4) but has yet to be described.

Figures 1–6. *Hortipes mesembrinus*. 1. Female habitus. 2, 5. Epigyne, ventral view. 3. Male palp, ventral view. 4. Same, retrolateral view. 6. Epigyne, dorsal view. Photo credits: 1–4 Charles Haddad. 5–6 From Bosselaers & Jocqué (2000).

Hortipes rothorum Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000

COMMON NAME: Roth's basket-legged spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic known only from the type locality, Jackson's Falls on the Mhlatuzana River, KwaZulu-Natal (EOO = <100 km²; AOO = 4 km²; 583 m a.s.l.). Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species' range. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal*: Mhlatuzana River, Jackson's Falls (-29.80, 30.75).

LIFESTYLE: This species is only known from leaf litter in woodland habitats in the Savanna Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species is threatened by loss of habitat for farming and infrastructure development.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the male (Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000).

Figures 1–2. *Hortipes rothorum*. 1. Male palp, ventral view. 2. Same, retrolateral view. From Bosselaers & Jocqué (2000).

Hortipes schoemanae Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000

COMMON NAME: Schoeman's basket-legged spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 2000 from Bergvliet Forest Station, Mpumalanga. The species has also been recorded from eSwatini. In South Africa, it is known from three provinces, including three protected areas: Ithala Game Reserve, Bergvliet Forest Station and Pretoria National Botanical Garden (EOO = 40 494 km²; AOO = 24 km²; 807–1303 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats known to the species, and due to its wide geographical range the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Swaziland and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Pretoria National Botanical Garden (-25.74, 28.19). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ithala Game Reserve, Doornkraal Camp (-27.51, 31.23). **Mpumalanga:** Barberton, Suid Kaap River (-25.79, 31.04); Bergvliet Forest Station, near Sabie (-25.10, 30.78); Schoemanskloof (-25.40, 30.50).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a ground-dweller collected from leaf litter and pitfall traps in indigenous forest and woodlands in the Forest, Grassland and Savanna biomes. Also sampled from commercial pine plantations.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000).

Figures 1–5. *Hortipes schoemanae*. 1. Female habitus. 2. Male palp, ventral view. 3. Same, retro-lateral view. 4. Epigyne, ventral view. 5. Same, dorsal view. Photo credits: 1 Peter Webb. 2–5 From Bosselaers & Jocqué (2000).

Hortipes wimmertensi Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000

COMMON NAME: Wimmertens' basket-legged spider

NATIONAL STATUS: CR

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described in 2000 from Oribi Gorge and also sampled from Port Shepstone (EOO = 100 km²; AOO = 8 km²; 66–410 m a.s.l.). It was last sampled in 1961. There is an on-going decline in suitable habitat for infrastructure development in parts of the species' range. Due to the species having a small restricted distribution range (<100 km²), it is listed as Critically Rare.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Oribi Gorge Nature Reserve (-30.69, 30.29); Port Shepstone (-30.74, 30.45).

LIFESTYLE: This species is strongly associated with leaf litter in woodland and forest habitats. It has been recorded from Eastern Valley Bushveld and the KwaZulu-Natal Coastal Belt in the Savanna Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: The species is threatened by loss of habitat for urbanization in Port Shepstone.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Bosselaers & Jocqué, 2000).

Figures 1–4. *Hortipes wimmertensi*. 1. Male palp, ventral view. 2. Same, retrolateral view. 3. Epigyne, ventral view. 4. Same, dorsal view. From Bosselaers & Jocqué (2000).

GENUS *MEDMASSA* Simon, 1887

Medmassa is an Old World genus represented by 11 species, of which only one occurs in the Afrotropical Region.

COMMON NAME: *Medmassa* dark sac spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Medmassa frenata* (Simon, 1877)

MORPHOLOGY: They are medium-sized spiders with a broad oval carapace. Their eyes are large and the posterior eye row is strongly procurved. Both sexes bear seven to ten pairs of ventral spines on the anterior tibiae. The genus can further be recognized by the presence of a male palpal retrolateral tibial apophysis that is often forked, the U-shaped sperm duct that lacks an additional loop, and the cymbium with a deep ventral furrow distally. The female epigyne has the copulatory openings located anteriorly and simple large round or oval spermathecae not divided into two distinct regions.

LIFESTYLE: They have been collected from tree bark at night.

TAXONOMY: Revised by Haddad & Bosselaers (2010).

Figures 1–2. *Medmassa semiaurantiaca*. 1. Female habitus. 2. Male eye pattern. Photo credits: Charles Haddad.

Medmassa semiaurantiaca Simon, 1910

COMMON NAME: *Medmassa* dark sac spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1910 from Guinée-Bissau. This species is also known from eight other African countries. In South Africa, it is known only from KwaZulu-Natal (EOO = 8 km²; AOO = 8 km²; 1–97 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species. Due to its wide geographical range in Africa, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Central African Republic, Democratic Republic of Congo, Ethiopia, Ghana, Guinée-Bissau, Kenya and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal*: iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Gwala-Gwala Forest (-28.38, 32.41); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Hell's Gate (-28.02, 32.26).

LIFESTYLE: This species is a rapidly-running nocturnally-active hunting spider that was commonly found on the bark of smooth-barked trees. Regularly collected during canopy fogging surveys in forests and savanna habitats in tropical Africa. Sampled from the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Forest biomes.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Redescribed by Haddad & Bosselaers (2010). Known from both sexes.

Figures 1–9. *Medmassa semiaurantiaca*. 1, 2. Female habitus. 3. Male habitus. 4, 6. Male palp, ventral view. 5, 8. Epigyne, ventral view. 7. Palp, retrolateral view. 9. Epigyne, dorsal view. Photo credits: 1, 4, 5 Charles Haddad. 2, 3, 6–9 From Haddad & Bosselaers (2010).

GENUS *MERENIUS* Simon, 1909

Merenius is known from Africa and Yemen and is represented by 12 species and subspecies.

COMMON NAME: Ornate ant-like sac spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Merenius plumosus* Simon, 1909

MORPHOLOGY: These are medium-sized spiders and with an elongate-oval carapace, oval abdomen and a sclerotized petiole. Their eyes are small and the posterior eye row is slightly recurved. The abdomen has distinct creamy-white to silvery-grey markings on a dark background.

LIFESTYLE: *Merenius* are exclusively ground-dwelling spiders that have a preference for habitats with a well-developed leaf litter layer. Most of the species could be considered generalized mimics of medium-sized ground-dwelling ants.

TAXONOMY: Most of the species have never been redescribed and several are only known from a single sex. The only recent paper on the genus is a redescription of *M. alberti* by Haddad & Louw (2012).

Figures 1–2. *Merenius alberti*. 1. Female habitus. 2. Male habitus. Photo credits: 1 Peter Webb. 2 Rudolph Steenkamp.

Merenius alberti Lessert, 1923

COMMON NAME: Albert's ant-like sac spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic species described in 1923 from Umbilo near Durban. Presently known from several southern African countries. In South Africa, the species is widespread, occurring in seven provinces (EOO = 493 246 km²; AOO = 236 km²; 4–1693 m a.s.l.), including >10 protected areas. Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mozambique, Zimbabwe, Swaziland and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Cwebbe Nature Reserve (-32.24, 28.91); Mazeppa Bay (-32.47, 28.64); Near Mazeppa Bay (-32.44, 28.61); Mkambati Nature Reserve (-31.26, 30.03). **Gauteng:** Johannesburg, Florida (-26.18, 27.91); Irene, Gem Village field (-25.89, 28.23). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Cathedral Peak (-28.96, 29.22); Dukuduku Forest (-28.37, 32.23); Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Durban, Bluff (-29.88, 31.02); Durban, Stella Bush (-29.89, 30.98); Durban, Umbilo (-29.88, 30.96); Empangeni (-28.75, 31.90); Enseleni Nature Reserve (-28.68, 32.05); Gwaliweni Forest (-27.38, 32.05); Hluhluwe-iMfolozi Park, Hilltop Research Station (-28.08, 32.04); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.10); Ingwavuma (-27.13, 32.00); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: Charter's Creek (-28.20, 32.43), Fanie's Island (-28.53, 32.40), Gwala-Gwala Forest (-28.38, 32.41), Hell's Gate (-28.00, 32.48), Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87), Lake Sibaya (-27.33, 32.70), Mapelane Nature Reserve (-28.41, 32.42), Mkuzi Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25), Sodwana Bay National Park (-27.40, 32.76) Umziki Pan (-27.97, 32.38); Mevamhlope (-28.73, 31.80); Mfongosi (-27.28, 32.15); Middel drift (-28.89, 31.04); Mtunzini, Twin Streams Farm (-28.95, 31.77); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.89, 32.32); Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45); Ngoye Forest (-28.84, 31.69); Nkandla Forest (-28.61, 31.09); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.39, 31.40); Otto's Bluff (-29.50, 30.36); Pietermaritzburg (-29.60, 30.38); Port Edward (-31.05, 30.22); Port Edward, Blencanthera Farm (-31.03, 30.17); Port Shepstone (-30.70, 30.46); Sheffield Beach (-29.48, 31.25); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Umhlali (-29.47, 31.22). **Limpopo:** Acornhoek (-24.60, 31.08); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16); Magoebaskloof (-23.86, 30.01). **Mpumalanga:** Burger's Hall (-25.10, 31.07); Crocodile River Gorge (-25.53, 31.22); Klaserie (-24.55, 31.03); Komatipoort (-25.44, 31.96); Komatipoort district, Farm Sommereg (-25.53, 31.82); Kruger National Park, Pretoriuskop Camp (-25.17, 31.25); Kruger National Park, Skukuza (-25.00, 31.97); Lisbon Falls, Graskop (-24.86, 30.84); Sabie (-25.09, 30.78). **North West:** Skeerpoort (-25.81, 27.77). **Western Cape:** Knysna (-33.87, 23.02).

Figures 1–10. *Merenius alberti*. 1. Male habitus, black morph. 2. Female habitus, red morph. 3, 7. Epigyne, ventral view. 4, 8. Same, dorsal view. 5, 9. Male palp, ventral view. 6, 10. Same, retrolateral view. Photo credits: 1 Rudolph Steenkamp. 2, 7–10 From Haddad & Louw (2012). 3–6 Charles Haddad.

Merenius alberti (continued)

LIFESTYLE: The species is an exclusive ground-dwelling spider and has mainly been collected by pitfall traps, litter sifting or by hand from the soil surface, under rocks and logs. Only on very rare occasions have specimens been collected by sweeping or beating. Sampled in leaf litter from the Forest, Grassland, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Savanna and Thicket biomes. It is one of the few South African ant-mimicking castianeirines whose biology has been studied in any detail (Haddad & Louw, 2012). *Merenius alberti* is polymorphic, with a widespread and common black morph with creamy-white to silvery-grey markings on the body, which is a generalized mimic of black ground-dwelling ants such as *Camponotus cinctellus*, whereas the red morph is a mimic of *Anoplolepis custodiens* ants. Females construct egg sacs on the underside of dead leaves, rocks and logs on the ground. Similar to other castianeirines, the egg sacs have a basal plate and a dome-shaped cover of papery silk, and are approximately 7.5 mm in diameter. Between 17–26 eggs are included in each sac. It is a typical generalist predator, feeding on crickets, termites, ants, flies and other spiders.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Redescribed by Haddad & Louw (2012). Known from both sexes.

Figures 1–4. *Merenius alberti*. 1. Female habitus, red morph. 2–4. Female habitus, black morph. Photo credits: 1, 2. Charles Haddad. 3, 4. Rudolph Steenkamp.

Merenius simoni Lessert, 1921

COMMON NAME: Simon's ant-like sac spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic species described in 1921 from the Democratic Republic of the Congo. The species was also collected in South Africa from the Limpopo Province and is protected in Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (EOO = 4 km²; AOO = 4 km²; 1341 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range in Africa, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of the Congo and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.04, 29.44).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a ground-dwelling spider and has mainly been collected by pitfall traps, litter sifting or by hand from the soil surface. Sampled from the Savanna biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, but known from both sexes and well-illustrated (Lessert, 1921).

Figures 1–6. *Merenius simoni*. 1. Subadult male habitus, dorsal view. 2. Same, anterior view. 3. Male habitus, dorsal view. 4. Male palp, prolateral view. 5. Embolus, ventral view. 6. Female abdomen, ventral view. Photo credits: 1, 2 Rudolph Steenkamp. 3–6 From Lessert (1921).

GENUS *MESSAPUS* Simon, 1898

Messapus is an African genus represented by seven species, three of which have been recorded from South Africa.

COMMON NAME: *Messapus* dark sac spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Messapus martini* Simon, 1898

MORPHOLOGY: These large spiders have an oval carapace with distinct markings resembling those of wolf spiders. The abdomen is oval, sometimes with mottled and chevron markings posteriorly. The eyes are large and the posterior eye row is slightly procurved. The anterior legs have only three pairs of ventral tibial spines.

LIFESTYLE: *Messapus* species are nocturnal arboreal hunters that are mainly found on tree bark, hunting at night. They are unique among the Afrotropical fauna in that they construct a silk retreat in crevices in trees or under bark in which they hide during the day and in which females construct their egg sacs. Specimens have occasionally been collected by canopy fogging, but generally these spiders are rare.

TAXONOMY: Revised by Haddad (2013c), with additional species subsequently described by Haddad & Mbo (2015). There are several new species from the Afrotropical Region that have been discovered since and await description.

Figures 1–2. *Messapus natalis*. 1. Female habitus. 2. Female retreat constructed in the knot of a tree trunk. Photo credits: Charles Haddad.

Messapus martini Simon, 1898

COMMON NAME: Martin's *Messapus* Dark Sac Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described in 1898, with the type locality only given as "Natal". The species is known from Zambia and South Africa. In South Africa, it has been recorded from three provinces and four protected areas (EOO= 55 616 km²; AOO= 48 km²; 5-1647 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Zambia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Groenkloof Nature Reserve (-25.79, 28.20); Wonderboom South (-25.70, 28.20); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve (-26.29, 28.08); Irene, Centurion, field opposite Gem Village (-25.89, 28.23). **Kwa-Zulu-Natal:** Dukuduku Forest (-28.37, 32.23); Hluhluwe-iMfolozi Park (-28.09, 32.04); Ingwavuma (-27.13, 32.00); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Charter's Creek (-28.20, 32.43), Hell's Gate (-28.00, 32.48); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.88, 32.31). **Mpumulanga:** Badplaas (-25.95, 30.57).

LIFESTYLE: This species is a free-living spider with contrasting habits, which has been collected from the soil surface, tree bark and tree canopies. Some specimens were observed actively hunting on bark at night. Both sexes were collected from dense silk retreats constructed in the fissures of bark of mature large trees, sampled from leaf litter, pit traps and canopy fogging. The species is known from the Forest, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Grassland and Savanna biomes, as well as synanthropic habitats.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species. Recorded from several protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Redescribed by Haddad (2013c). Known from both sexes.

Figures 1–8. *Messapus martini*. 1, 3. Female habitus. 2, 4. Male habitus. 5, 6. Male palp, ventral view. 7, 8. Epigyne, ventral view. Photo credits: 1–5, 7 Charles Haddad. 6, 8 From Haddad (2013c).

Messapus meridionalis Haddad & Mbo, 2015

COMMON NAME: Southern *Messapus* Dark Sac Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described in 2015 and known only from the type locality, Oribi Gorge Nature Reserve (EOO = 4 km²; AOO = 4 km²; 416 m a.s.l.). It is possibly under-collected and more localities are suspected to occur. The status of the species remains obscure. More sampling is needed to collect the male and determine the species' range. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: KwaZulu-Natal: Oribi Gorge Nature Reserve, Samango waterfall trail (-30.71, 30.26).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living spider. Sampled during canopy fogging in riparian forest in the Savanna Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known only from the female (Haddad & Mbo, 2015).

Figures 1–3. *Messapus meridionalis*. 1. Female habitus. 2, 3. Epigyne, ventral view. 4, 5. Same, dorsal view. Photo credits: 1–3, 5 From Haddad & Mbo (2015). 4 Charles Haddad.

Messapus natalis (Pocock, 1898)

COMMON NAME: Giant *Messapus* dark sac spider.

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic species described in 1898 as *Corinna natalis* from Durban, South Africa. The species is presently also known from Mozambique. In South Africa, it has been sampled from three provinces and is conserved in three protected areas: Ndumo Game Reserve, Lowveld National Botanical Gardens and Dukuduku Forest (EOO = 55 352 km²; AOO = 36 km²; 17–975 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range and no known threats, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Mozambique, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **KwaZulu-Natal:** Dukuduku Forest (-28.37, 32.23); Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Ifafa Beach (-30.45, 30.64); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Cape Vidal (-28.16, 32.56); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Mission Rocks Beach (-28.27, 32.48); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Hell's Gate (-28.02, 32.26); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Umhlatuze River mouth (-28.81, 31.94). **Limpopo:** Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45). **Mpumulanga:** Crocodile River Gorge (-25.53, 31.22); Lowveld National Botanical Gardens (-25.47, 31.00).

LIFESTYLE: *Messapus natalis* is primarily an arboreal species, as some of the specimens were distinctly collected from retreats constructed in fissures or similar structures on tree bark, or in canopy fogging samples. Collected from the Forest, Savanna and Indian Ocean Coastal Belt biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Redescribed by Haddad (2013b). Known from both sexes. It is the largest described species of Corinnidae from Africa known to date.

Figures 1–10. *Messapus natalis*. 1, 2. Female habitus. 3. Male habitus. 4, 5. Retreats constructed in trees. 6. Male palp, prolateral view. 7. Same, ventral view. 8. Same, retrolateral view. 9. Epigyne, ventral view. 10. Same, dorsal view. Photo credits: 1 Christopher Willis. 2–5 Charles Haddad. 6–10 From Haddad (2005).

GENUS *PRONOPHAEA* Simon, 1897

Pronophaea is an South African endemic genus currently represented by three species.

COMMON NAME: *Pronophaea* Dark Sac Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Pronophaea natalica* Simon, 1897

MORPHOLOGY: Medium-sized spiders, between 4 and 8 mm in total length, and usually dark in colour. Carapace broad, with narrowed eye region, posterior margin concave. Surface covered in fine tubercles bearing short fine setae. Abdomen oval, males with broad scutum covering most of dorsum, absent in females. Abdomen oval, with or without chevron markings dorsally. Anterior legs much longer and more robust than posterior legs, anterior tibiae usually with 5–7 pairs of ventral spines and metatarsi with 2–3 pairs of ventral spines. Anterior femora with 2–4 strong prolateral spines. Male palp with oval cymbium and tegulum, embolus and conductor originating prolaterally and directed retrolaterally. Tegulum bearing a fine curved median apophysis. Female epigyne with paired or single median atrium, with small posterior spermathecae.

LIFESTYLE: All *Pronophaea* are ground-dwellers and are usually associated with leaf litter in the Forest, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Thicket and Savanna biomes. A few species have been collected in the Grassland Biome, where they are typically found sheltering under rocks or at the bases of grass tussocks.

TAXONOMY: Partly revised by Haddad & Bosselaers (2010). There are several new species from South Africa and Lesotho.

Figures 1–2. *Pronophaea natalica*, female habitus. Photo credits: 1 Charles Haddad. 2 Rudolph Steenkamp.

Pronophaea natalica Simon, 1897

COMMON NAME: Natal *Pronophaea* dark sac spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 1897, with the type locality only given as Natal. The species has a wide distribution and has been sampled from six provinces. It is conserved in >10 protected areas (EOO = 764 836 km²; AOO = 216 km²; 3–1861 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Cwebe Nature Reserve (-32.24, 28.91); East London (-33.01, 27.90); Hogsback (-32.60, 26.94); Jeffrey's Bay (-34.04, 24.92); Kei Mouth (-32.68, 28.37); Keurkloof, Baviaanskloof (-33.68, 24.83); King William's Town (-32.73, 27.28); Mazeppa Bay (-32.47, 28.64); Mkambati Nature Reserve (-31.26, 30.03); Mount Frere (-30.90, 29.00); Near Mazeppa Bay (-32.44, 28.61); Prentjiesberg (-31.07, 28.19); Thomas Baines Nature Reserve (-33.38, 26.48); Umngazi River Mouth (-31.68, 29.45). **Free State:** Tussen-die-Riviere Nature Reserve (-30.47, 26.12). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Baynesfield (-29.76, 30.35); Cathedral Peak (-28.96, 29.22); Empangeni (-28.75, 31.90); 15 km N of Richards Bay (-28.83, 32.08); Gwaliweni Forest (-27.38, 32.05); Hluhluwe-iMfolozi Park, Hilltop Research Station (-28.08, 32.04); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.10); Indumeni (-28.23, 30.23); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Eastern Shores Nature Reserve (-29.09, 32.16); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Hell's Gate (-27.58, 32.67); Kamberg Nature Reserve (-29.38, 29.62); Karkloof Nature Reserve (-29.36, 30.19); Lotheni Nature Reserve (-29.42, 29.53); Mtunzini (-28.96, 31.76); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.91, 32.32); New Hanover (-29.35, 30.53); Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45); Ngoye Forest (-28.84, 31.69); Nongoma (-27.90, 31.72); Oribi Gorge Nature Reserve (-30.58, 30.00); Otto's Bluff (-29.50, 30.36); Pietermaritzburg (-29.60, 30.38); Port Edward (-31.05, 30.22); Richmond (-29.87, 30.28); Sani Pass (-29.66, 29.51); Scottburgh (-30.29, 30.75); Umgeni Valley Nature Reserve (-29.47, 30.20); Umhlali (-29.48, 31.23); Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve (-30.27, 23.33); Weza Forest (-30.53, 29.69). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.04, 29.44). **Mpumalanga:** Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87). **Western Cape:** Borrelfontein, 8 km W of Gouritz River Mouth (-34.33, 21.85); Brenton-on-Sea (-34.08, 23.04); De Hoop Nature Reserve, Potberg (-34.37, 20.53); Fernkloof Nature Reserve (-34.40, 19.27); Fisherhaven (-34.47, 19.13); Lily Vlei Nature Reserve (-33.64, 19.47).

Figures 1–8. *Pronophaea natalica*. 1–5. Female habitus. 6. Male habitus. 7. Male palp, ventral view. 8. Epigyne, ventral view. Photo credits: 1, 2 Rudolph Steenkamp. 3, 4 Ruan Booysen. 5–8 Charles Had-dad.

Pronophaea natalica (continued)

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground-dwellers collected predominantly in leaf litter and pitfall traps. Sampled from all the floral biomes except the Desert and Succulent Karoo biomes. Also sampled from commercial pine plantations.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Redescribed by Haddad & Bosselaers (2010). It is a senior synonym of *Medmassa nitida* Lawrence, 1937, which was described from KwaZulu-Natal. Known from both sexes, illustrated.

Figures 1–6. *Pronophaea natalica*. 1. Female habitus, dorsal view. 2. Same, lateral view. 3. Epigyne, ventral view. 4. Male habitus, dorsal view. 5. Same, lateral view. 6. Male palp, ventral view. From Haddad & Bosselaers (2010).

Pronophaea proxima (Lessert, 1923)

COMMON NAME: Zebra *Pronophaea* dark sac spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 1923 as *Medmassa proxima* from Krantzkloof, KwaZulu-Natal. The species is known from four provinces and protected in two protected areas, Groeneweide Forest Station and Nylsvley Nature Reserve (EOO = 344 374 km²; AOO = 20 km²; 19–1097 m a.s.l.). The species has a wide geographical range and is listed as being of Least Concern

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Mazeppa Bay (-32.47, 28.64); Coffee Bay (-31.97, 29.14). **Western Cape:** Groeneweide Forest Station (-33.95, 22.46). **Limpopo:** Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Krantzkloof (-29.77, 30.83).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground-dwellers. Sampled from the Grassland and Savanna biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Haddad & Bosselaers (2010) illustrated the male. The female has not yet been described.

Figures 1–2. *Pronophaea proxima*. 1. Male habitus. 2. Palp, ventral view. From Haddad & Bosselaers (2010).

Pronophaea vidua (Lessert, 1923)

COMMON NAME: Midlands *Pronophaea* dark sac spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 1923 as *Medmassa vidua* from Krantzkloof, KwaZulu-Natal. The species is known from two localities only (EOO = 5153 km²; AOO = 8 km²; 344–1002 m a.s.l.). The species has a wide geographical range and can be listed as being of Least Concern

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Krantzkloof Nature Reserve (-29.77, 30.83). *KwaZulu-Natal:* Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dwellers. Sampled from the Grassland and Savanna biomes.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Haddad & Bosselaers (2010) illustrated the female, but the male has not yet been described.

Figures 1–2. *Pronophaea vidua*. 1. Female habitus. 2. Epigyne, ventral view. From Haddad & Bosselaers (2010).

GENUS *VENDAPHAEA* Haddad, 2009

COMMON NAME: Furry-legged dark sac spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Vendaphaea lajuma* Haddad, 2009

MORPHOLOGY: This genus can be recognized from other corinnids by the closely spaced posterior median eyes, densely setose and strongly spined anterior legs, and the uniquely shaped female epigyne and palpal morphology. Medium-sized spiders, 6.03–7.85 mm in length. Carapace oval, eye region narrow, fovea distinct; posterior margin slightly concave; carapace red-brown, densely setose, surface finely granulate. Abdomen densely covered in short mottled grey-brown setae, with short black dorsal chevron markings, each ending in white spot; dorsal scutum absent in both sexes.

LIFESTYLE: The species was initially collected by Foord *et al.* (2008) from leaf litter of mixed woodland habitats in the Soutpansberg, where subsequent samples were also collected from montane savannah.

TAXONOMY: Described by Haddad (2009).

Figure 1. *Vendaphaea lajuma*, male habitus. Photo credit: Charles Haddad

Vendaphaea lajuma Haddad, 2009

COMMON NAME: Furry-legged dark sac spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Limpopo endemic described in 2009 from Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (was Lajuma Mountain Retreat). The species is known from three Limpopo localities, which are 178.43 km apart (EOO = 3184 km²; AOO = 12 km²; 1172–1605 m a.s.l.). The species is under-collected and more sampling is needed to determine its range. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Bela-Bela, ATKV Klein Kariba Resort (-24.85, 28.33); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.04, 29.44); Naboomspruit, Rhemardo Holiday Resort (-24.44, 28.60).

LIFESTYLE: The species is a free-running ground-dweller. Sampled from the leaf litter of mixed woodland and forest habitats, as well as forests, woodlands and grassland patches in the Soutpansberg. It has also been found at the bases of grass tussocks in the Savanna Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no known threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from both sexes (Haddad, 2009).

Figures 1–9. *Vendaphaea lajuma*. 1, 2. Male habitus. 3. Female habitus. 4. Same, eye region. 5, 6. Male palp, ventral view. 7. Same, retrolateral view. 8, 9. Epigyne, ventral view. Photo credits: 1, 4, 5, 8. Charles Haddad. 2, 3, 6, 9 From Haddad (2009).

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